

A biotechnological study on biosurfactants for drug delivery applications

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I declare that no part of the work referred to in this thesis has been submitted in support of an application for another degree or qualification of this or any other university or other institute of learning.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ANOVA	: Analysis of variance
Bax	: BCL-2 associated X protein
BCL2	: B-cell lymphoma 2
BS	: Biosurfactant
CMC	: Critical micelle concentration
CO₂	: Carbon dioxide
CV%	: Coefficient of variation
Da	: Dalton
DMEM	: Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium
DMSO	: Dimethylsulfoxide
DTA	: Differential thermal analysis
DRI	: Dose reduction index
E24	: Emulsifying index at 24 h
EE%	: Entrapment efficiency
EDTA	: Ethylenediamine tetraacetic acid
ESI-MS	: Electrospray ionization mass spectrometry
FTIR	: Fourier transform infrared
GC	: Gas chromatography
GRAS	: Generally recognized as safe
HCl	: Hydrochloric acid
HPLC	: High pressure liquid chromatography
IC₅₀	: Half-maximal inhibitory concentration
LBS	: Lipopeptide biosurfactant
LBS nSAs	: Lipopeptide biosurfactant nano self-assemblies
LE%	: Loading efficiency
MDR	: Multi-drug resistance
MEL	: Mannosylerythritol lipids

MTT	: 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide
mRNA	: Messenger ribonucleic acid
PBS	: Phosphate buffer saline
PDI	: Polydispersity index
PG	: Prodigiosin
PG-LBS nSAs	: Prodigiosin-lipopeptide biosurfactant nano self- assemblies
R²	: Correlation coefficient
RBCs	: Red blood cells
SD	: Standard deviation
SF	: Surfactant
SPE	: Solid phase extraction
TEM	: Transmission electron microscopy
TGA	: Thermogravimetric analysis
ζ-potential	: Zeta potential

1. INTRODUCTION

Biosurfactants are microbially derived surface active agents that are rapidly emerging as ecofriendly and effective substitutes to synthetic surface active agents conventionally utilized in diverse industries including pharmaceutical manufacturing. Biosurfactants are amphiphilic multifunctional bioactive secondary metabolites produced by bacteria, yeasts, and fungi of different species and strains. The high surface activity, bioactivity, low toxicity, biocompatibility, and biodegradability of biosurfactants render them an important product of bioeconomy and the next generation multifunctional biomolecules ^(4,5).

Biosurfactants offer great prospects in the pharmaceutical field. These include potential utilization of biosurfactants as wetting, cleansing, solubilizing and emulsifying agents in pharmaceutical, personal care and detergent formulations ⁽⁶⁾. In addition, biosurfactants possess drug-like actions, justifying their investigation as anti-microbial, anti-inflammatory, and anti-tumor agents ⁽⁷⁾.

Finally, biosurfactants may play multiple roles as formulation components in drug delivery systems with well-established advantages over conventional formulations ⁽⁸⁾. Among these, drug entrapment in the inherently self-assembled nano-sized micelle-like clusters of biosurfactants was shown to enhance the activity of different entrapped drugs such as insulin ⁽⁹⁾, doxorubicin ⁽¹⁰⁾ and bleomycin ⁽¹¹⁾. However, the application of biosurfactants in drug delivery is still in its infancy and further research efforts are warranted to maximize the benefit of merging biotechnology and pharmaceutical nanotechnology for the development of bionanotechnology-based drug delivery systems.

2. AIM OF THE WORK

This work aims to produce a lipopeptide biosurfactant from *Bacillus licheniformis* SHG10 DSMZ28096, not explored to date as biosurfactant producer and to evaluate its potential as drug carrier using prodigiosin, a secondary bacterial metabolite, as anti-tumor agent.

3. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

3.1. Biosurfactants: An overview

In recent years, increasing awareness of environmental hazards and the related legislations have presented a powerful driving force for the exploration of sustainable, and ecofriendly materials for diverse industries and applications. Because of their favorable properties including high surface activity, sustainability, and physicochemical stability, surfactants of microbial origin (microbial biosurfactants, or simply biosurfactants) are expected to play a prominent role in this respect. Biosurfactants are amphiphilic bioactive secondary metabolites produced by bacteria, yeasts, and fungi of different species and strains either extracellularly or as part of the cell membrane⁽¹²⁾ using the organic waste produced mainly by the food, agriculture, and oil industry as carbon source. The use of microbes for utilization of this carbon dioxide (CO₂)-liberating waste for the production of value-added products such as bioplastics, biofuels, and biosurfactants increases the economics of the process and contributes to environmental sustainability⁽¹³⁾.

Excellent producers of biosurfactants include *Pseudomonas*, *Bacillus* and *Acinetobacter* genera. Nevertheless, yeasts and yeast-like fungi such as *Starmerella bombicola* and non-pathogenic bacteria are attracting more attention as microorganisms with a lower risk of toxicity or pathogenicity⁽⁷⁾. The diversity of producer microorganisms has led to the generation of biosurfactants of various molecular characteristics, and consequently physicochemical and biological properties⁽¹⁴⁾. The huge number of literature reports and patents which explore new biosurfactant types, properties and applications translated into a wide range of potential applications. This rendered biosurfactants an important product of bio-economy and the next generation multifunctional biomolecules^(12, 15, 16).

Biosurfactants can be defined as amphipathic molecules featuring both hydrophobic and hydrophilic moieties capable of efficiently decreasing the surface tension at the air-water and the interfacial tension at the oil-water mixture. Surface activity of biosurfactants is a primary determinant of their utility in different applications. This is promoted by an array of advantages including sustainability attributed to renewability of materials or residues used in their microbial production, biodegradability, low toxicity, and environmental capability⁽¹⁷⁾. In addition, biological multi-functionality of biosurfactants provides the basis for a wide spectrum of biomedical applications. As such, biosurfactants are expanding as an eco-friendly alternative to conventional chemically-synthesized surfactants. However, in spite of their great advantages, biosurfactants have some limitations mainly restricted to the difficulties encountered in the scaling up of their production, a challenge faced by ongoing research into advanced and more economic biotechnological production protocols involving engineered hyper-producing microbial strains and optimization of cultivation parameters^(13, 18, 19).

3.2. Classification of biosurfactants

Biosurfactants can be classified according to their chemical structure, molecular weight, microbial origin, or mode of action^(15, 20). The hydrophobic part of the biosurfactant molecule is commonly a linear, branched, saturated, unsaturated, or hydroxylated fatty acid while the hydrophilic part usually consists of a peptide, amino acid, monosaccharide, disaccharide, or polysaccharide. According to their chemical structure, biosurfactants can be classified mainly into (i) glycolipids, (ii) lipopeptides, (iii) fatty acids, phospholipids, and neutral lipids, (iv) polymeric

and (v) vesicular biosurfactants ⁽²¹⁾. Examples of biosurfactants and their main examples are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Main chemical classes of biosurfactants

3.2.1. Glycolipid biosurfactants

Glycolipid biosurfactant molecules have two types of moieties: fatty acid lipid moiety(ies) linked with a covalent glycosidic bond to polar head(s) consisting of different polysaccharides, mainly rhamnose, trehalose, sophorose, or mannose ⁽¹⁵⁾. Glycolipids are classified according to their hydrophilic head and hydrophobic tail into the main subclasses: rhamnolipids, trehalolipids, sophorolipids, and mannosyl erythritol lipids (MEL). The chemical structures of the main types of glycolipid biosurfactants are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The chemical structure of the main types of glycolipid biosurfactants ⁽²²⁾

3.2.1.1. Rhamnolipids

Rhamnolipids are produced mainly by *P. aeruginosa*. They are distinguished by one or two molecules of the sugar rhamnose coupled to one or two molecules of hydroxydecanoic acid. Rhamnolipids are generally produced by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Burkholderia* sp. and are known as one of the most effective types of surfactants in the remediation of hydrophobic compounds from contaminated soils ⁽²³⁾, oil recovery ⁽²⁴⁾ and biomedicine as potential antimicrobial and anticancer agents ^(25, 26) and for wounds healing applications ⁽²⁷⁾.

3.2.1.2. Trehalolipids

Trehalolipids constitute a broad subclass of glycolipids consisting of a double sugar compound of trehalose attached with mycolic acids. Trehalolipids are produced mainly by *Mycobacterium*, *Corynebacterium*, and *Rhodococcus* sp., and their structure differs according to the microbial producer ^(28, 29). Trehalolipids from nonpathogenic *Rhodococcus* sp show immunomodulatory activities by interacting with immunocompetent cells ⁽³⁰⁾.

3.2.1.3. Sophorolipids

Sophorolipids are composed of a dimeric carbohydrate sophorose coupled with a long-chain hydroxyl fatty acid by a glycosidic linkage. Yeast strains, particularly *Candida bombicola*, *C. apicola*, as well as *C. bogoriensis* are producers of sophorolipids⁽³¹⁾. At most, a mixture of six to nine various hydrophobic sophorolipids and lactone form the sophorolipids which are desirable for several applications. Sophorolipids are among the most important glycolipid biosurfactants in different industrial sectors⁽³²⁾. They also exert antimicrobial activity against bacteria⁽³³⁾, fungi⁽³⁴⁾ and Covid-19 virus⁽³⁵⁾.

3.2.1.4. Mannosylerythritol lipids (MEL)

Mannosylerythritol lipid (MEL) biosurfactants are structurally composed of 4-*O*- β -d-mannopyranosyl-*Meso*-erythritol and lipids with a hydrophilic head and hydrophobic head-tail, respectively⁽³⁶⁾. MEIs are produced mainly by anamorphic basidiomycetous yeasts, *Pseudozyma spp.*, and by fungi of the genera *Pseudozyma* and *Ustilago*⁽³⁷⁾. MELs have distinct antimicrobial properties^(38,39) and are well-known for their application in the personal care and cosmetic industry^(6,40).

3.2.2. Lipopeptides and lipoproteins

Lipopeptides and lipoproteins constitute one of the largest classes of biosurfactants. They are generally produced from bacterial *Bacillus* and *Pseudomonas* genera⁽⁴¹⁾. The lipopeptide structure includes a C₁₂ - C₁₈ fatty acid linked to a peptide chain of 4 to 12 amino acids⁽⁴²⁾. Lipopeptides may have a linear hydrophilic head or a lactone ring if they have a cyclic structure. Cyclic lipopeptides include mainly surfactins, iturins, lichenysins, viscosins, and amphisins. Among lipopeptide biosurfactants, surfactin (Figure 3) is prominent for its high surface activity and multiple biological activities⁽⁴³⁾. For example, surfactin as a promising functional ingredient of cosmetic and personal care products, and household detergents⁽⁶⁾ and as emulsifying agent in pharmaceutical formulations⁽⁴⁴⁾. The chemical structure of lipopeptide biosurfactants confers antimicrobial activity and inhibition of biofilms produced by bacteria and fungi^(45,46) as well as antiviral activity⁽⁴⁷⁾. Surfactin cyclic lipopeptides are also reported to modify the composition and lateral organization of the plasma membrane of mammalian cells, a property probably involved in the inhibition of cancer cells⁽⁴⁸⁾. Lipopeptide biosurfactants including surfactin were also reported to exhibit anti-cancer activity⁽⁴⁹⁾. The delivery of surfactin as anticancer agent can be enhanced by nanotechnological methods⁽⁵⁰⁾.

Figure 3: Chemical structure of surfactin⁽⁴³⁾

Another lipopeptide biosurfactant is lichenysin produced by *Bacillus licheniformis* ⁽⁵¹⁾. Lichenysin contains a peptide moiety with seven amino acids and a β -hydroxy fatty acid of 12–17 carbon atoms. Lichenysin is available in different isoforms, the most abundant one being lichenysin A. This is an anionic lipopeptide biosurfactant with cytotoxic, antimicrobial, and hemolytic activities, possessing enormous potential for chemical and biological applications ^(52, 53). Lichenysin A is very similar to surfactin, differing only by 1 Da in molecular mass, attributable to the substitution of glutamic acid for glutamine in the first amino acid position. This small difference remarkably affects the physicochemical properties of lichenysin, in particular regarding surface tension reduction ⁽⁵⁴⁾.

3.2.3. Fatty acids, phospholipids, and neutral lipids

Several bacteria and yeasts can produce considerable amounts of fatty acids and phospholipid surfactants while grown on culture media containing n-alkanes. Among fatty acids, Corynomycolic acids and spiculisporic acid are much more effective surfactants relative to simple fatty acids. An example of phospholipid biosurfactants are phosphatidylethanolamines produced by bacteria as extracellular membrane vesicles ⁽⁵⁵⁾.

3.2.4. Polymeric biosurfactants

Numerous bacterial species from different genera produce exocellular polymeric surfactants consisting of protein, polysaccharides, lipoproteins, lipopolysaccharides, or complex mixtures of these biopolymers. These include emulsan, liposan, alasan, lipomanan and other polysaccharide-protein complexes. Polymeric biosurfactants can be used as efficient emulsifying agents in the food and cosmetics industries ⁽⁵⁶⁾. Moreover, polymeric biosurfactants, such as emulsan, were used in the formulation of nanoparticles as a nanocarrier for pheophorbide as a model hydrophobic drug with improved drug activity ⁽⁵⁷⁾.

3.2.5. Particulate biosurfactants

Particulate biosurfactants are produced by some bacteria in the extracellular space. They are present in the form of vesicles that can form microemulsions that affect mobility in the hydrocarbon medium and alkane uptake of the cell ⁽⁵⁸⁾. As shown in Figure 1, particulate biosurfactants include vesicles and whole microbial cells. Vesicles consist of a phospholipid bilayer surrounding a lumen or interior space. These are membrane-bound organelles necessary for transporting material within the cell. An example of this type of biosurfactant presenting emulsifying activity is the vesicles produced by *Acinetobacter spp.* strain HO1-N having a diameter of 20 to 50 nm and composed of proteins, phospholipids, and lipopolysaccharides ⁽⁵⁹⁾.

Regarding whole bacterial cells, it has been demonstrated that bacterial cell itself can be considered a biosurfactant. For example, suspensions of bacterial cells may reduce surface and interfacial tension and exhibit emulsifying properties. This can be attributed to the composition of cell surface featuring hydrophobic and hydrophilic sections ⁽⁶⁰⁾. Entire bacterial cells such as those of *Acinetobacter calcoaceticus* 2CA2, were shown to act as emulsifying agents and to produce extracellular emulsifiers ⁽⁶¹⁾.

3.3. Microorganisms-producing biosurfactants

Many microorganisms including bacteria, fungi, and yeast are considered potential producers of biosurfactants ⁽⁶²⁾. Microorganisms which produce biosurfactants are isolated from sites which present or were contaminated by petroleum hydrocarbons. This usually occurs since, in nature, biosurfactants play a physiologic role in increasing bioavailability of hydrophobic molecules which are involved in cellular signaling and differentiation processes, which facilitate the consumption of carbon sources present in soil. These microorganisms have the potential to degrade many hydrocarbons for use as carbon sources and encapsulate heavy metals and/or hydrocarbons through the production of active surfactants, the biosurfactants ⁽⁶³⁾. The type, quantity, and quality of biosurfactants are mostly influenced by the nature of the carbon substrate used by the producer microorganism and the culture conditions including temperature, pH, and agitation.

Bacteria

Bacteria are excellent producers of biosurfactants production. (Table 1) shows a list of representative bacteria used in the production of biosurfactants and the type of biosurfactant produced.

Table 1: Representative examples of some biosurfactants-producing bacteria

Bacteria	Biosurfactant	References
Bacillus subtilis	Surfactin and iturin A	(64)
B.licheniformis	Surfactin and lichenysin	(53)
B. brevis	Gramicidin	(65)
B. amyloliquefaciens	Surfactin and iturin A	(66)
Serratia marcescens	Serrawettin	(67)
S. rubidea	Rhamnolipids	(68)
P. fluorescens	Viscosin	(69)
P. aeruginosa	Rhamnolipids	(70)
Torulopsis apicola	Sophrolipids	(71)
Acinetobacter calcoaceticus	Emulsan	(72)
Rhodococcus	Glycolipids	(73)

Fungi

Although the production of biosurfactants by bacteria has been the subject of several investigations, information about biosurfactants-producing fungi is scarce (74). Fungi reported to produce biosurfactants include mainly *Candida bombicola*, *Candida lipolytica*, *Candida ishiwadae*, *Candida batistae*, *Aspergillus ustus* and *Trichosporon ashii*. Fungi have the ability to produce biosurfactants upon growing on low-cost substrate. It is worth mentioning that co-

cultures of biosurfactant-producing bacteria and fungi enhanced the production of biosurfactants⁽⁷⁵⁾. Table 2 shows some examples of fungi reported as biosurfactant producers.

Table 2: Representative examples of some biosurfactant-producing fungi

Fungus	biosurfactant	References
<i>Candida Antarctica</i>	Mannosylerythritol lipid	(76)
<i>Candida bombicola</i>	Sophorous lipids	(77)
<i>Candida tropicalis</i>	Mannan-fatty acid	(78)
<i>Candida lipolytica Y-917</i>	Sophorous lipid	(79)
<i>Candida lipolytica UCP0988</i>	Carbohydrate–protein–lipid complex	(80)
<i>Corynebacterium hydrocarbolasus</i>	Protein–lipid carbohydrate	(81)
<i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i>	Polypeptide derivative	(82)
<i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i>	Monoketide derivative	(83)
<i>Yarrowia lipolytica IMUFRJ 50682</i>	Carbohydrate protein complex	(84)
<i>Ustilago maydis</i>	Cellobiose lipids	(85)
<i>Nocardia erythropolis</i>	Neutral lipids	(86)
<i>Aspergillus versicolor</i>	Chromone derivative	(87)
<i>Torulopsis bombicola</i>	Sophorose lipids	(88)
<i>Ochrobactrum anthropi</i>	Protein	(89)

Yeasts

Yeasts are producer of safer biosurfactants because of their generally regarded as safe (GRAS) status. Microorganisms which feature a GRAS status would not present a risk of inducing toxicity and pathogenic reactions, a fact that increases the range of possible uses of biosurfactants obtained from these microorganisms, particularly in the food and pharmaceutical industries. Moreover, yeasts produce biosurfactants in higher concentrations than bacteria, offering an economic advantage^(90, 91). The yeast productivity of biosurfactants can be increased by new technologies⁽⁹²⁾. Representative biosurfactant-producing yeasts are listed in (Table 3).

Table 3: Representative examples of biosurfactant-producing yeasts

Yeast	Biosurfactants	References
<i>Torulopsis petrophilum</i>	Sophorolipids	(93)
<i>Torulopsis apicola</i>	Sophorolipids	(94)
<i>Pseudozyma rugulosa</i>	Mannosylerythritol lipids	(95)
<i>Pseudozyma aphidi</i>	Mannosylerythritol lipids	(96)
<i>Pseudozyma siamensis</i>	Mannosylerythritol lipids	(97)
<i>Pseudozyma fusiformata</i>	Mannosylerythritol lipids	(98)
<i>Kurtzmanomyces sp.</i>	Mannosylerythritol lipids	(99)
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	Mannanoprotein	(100)
<i>Kluyveromyces marxianus</i>	Mannanoprotein	(101)

3.4. Main functional properties of biosurfactants

Surface activity is a fundamental property of surfactants including biosurfactants that plays a critical role in the development and performance evaluation of different surfactant-based products. In fact, surface activity of biosurfactants and the directly associated wetting, detergency, cleansing, foaming, emulsifying and antimicrobial properties of biosurfactants are vital to different biosurfactant applications. The functional properties of biosurfactants have been the subject of excellent recent reviews ^(14, 102).

3.4.1. Surface activity

By virtue of their amphiphilic nature, biosurfactants are characterized by surface activity which is the tendency to adsorb at the air/liquid, liquid/liquid or solid/liquid interfaces in an oriented fashion leading to lowering of surface tension and interfacial tension, respectively. In addition, surfactants self-assemble into organized molecular assemblies known as micelles at the critical micelle concentration (CMC)⁽¹⁵⁾. At low concentration, biosurfactant monomers accumulate at the air/liquid interface of an aqueous solution resulting in a concentration dependent reduction of surface tension till the CMC is reached. Above the CMC, biosurfactant monomers spontaneously form micelles with different morphologies ^(102, 103). The relationship between biosurfactant concentration, surface tension and formation of micelles ⁽²⁾ is illustrated in Figure 4. Micellar self-assemblies play an important role in the solubilization of oils and insoluble drugs by biosurfactants ⁽¹⁰⁴⁻¹⁰⁶⁾.

Figure 4: The relationship between biosurfactant concentration, surface tension and micelle formation ⁽²⁾.

The surface activity of biosurfactants determine their efficiency which is the ability to self-assemble at low concentration and effectiveness, the ability to reduce the liquid/liquid, and solid/liquid interfacial tension ⁽¹⁰⁷⁾. Efficiency and effectiveness affect the functional properties of biosurfactants including mainly wetting, self-assembly and micellar solubilization as well emulsification, all critical to different applications.

3.4.2. Wetting properties

Wetting of water repellent substrates such as hydrophobic powders, oils, and greasy surfaces by aqueous solutions is of great importance in the pharmaceutical dispersion of hydrophobic powders and the performance of surfactant- and biosurfactant-based cleansing, washing, detergent, and cleaning products. Wettability is the ability of a liquid to spread over a solid surface ⁽¹⁰⁸⁾. Wettability is usually measured as a decrease of the contact angle of a liquid droplet, the angle measured at the liquid / air interface on a hydrophobic surface ⁽¹⁰⁹⁾. Surfactants including biosurfactants at concentrations below the CMC can be used to increase the wettability of hydrophobic substrates by adsorption of the surfactant molecules via its hydrophobic tail, reducing the interfacial tension at the water/substrate interface and mobilizing the substrate. The wetting properties of biosurfactants may be of great importance in pharmaceutical formulation ⁽¹¹⁰⁾, soil remediation ⁽¹¹¹⁾] and other biotechnological applications ⁽¹¹²⁻¹¹⁴⁾.

3.4.3. Solubilizing properties

Spontaneous self-assembly of surfactants at the CMC into micelles capable of incorporating an insoluble substrate (solubilizate) such as oils and insoluble drugs is a well-documented solubilization mechanism, referred to as micellar solubilization ⁽¹¹⁵⁻¹¹⁷⁾. The structural properties of the solubilizate and surfactant determine the extent of micellar solubilization and the locus of solubilizate in the micelles. Hydrophobic substrates are usually entrapped within the hydrophobic domains of the micellar nanostructure ^(115, 118). Like synthetic surfactants, biosurfactants form micelles in aqueous media at their CMC, typically in the concentration range 1 to 200 mg/L ⁽¹¹⁹⁾. Biosurfactants form different

types of micelles ^(102, 120) via hydrogen bonding, hydrophobic, and van der Waals interactions ⁽¹²¹⁾. The size, shape and number of micelles are affected by the molecular characteristics and concentration of the biosurfactant in addition to the medium pH, salt content, and temperature ^(120, 122). Micelle formation by biosurfactants is essential to bioremediation processes ^(106, 123) and the removal of oils, stains and insoluble residues by cleansing personal care, detergent and cleaning products ⁽¹²⁴⁾. Moreover, surfactin and sophorolipid biosurfactants were also shown to solubilize insoluble drugs ⁽¹⁰⁵⁾. Interestingly, some rhamnolipid biosurfactants may effectively solubilize insoluble substrates at sub-CMC concentrations, reducing the usage of biosurfactant ⁽¹²⁵⁾.

3.4.4. Emulsifying properties

Emulsions are very versatile liquid disperse systems used in a wide range of industries including the chemical, energy, food, pharmaceutical, cosmetic, agricultural as well as the detergent / cleaning industries ^(126, 127). Apart from its importance as a process in developing emulsified products, emulsification is an essential step in the detergency mechanism, allowing for mixing and removal of water-resistant soils and stains from various substrates ^(128, 129). Emulsions can be classified according to their type into oil-in-water (o/w), water-in-oil (w/o) and multiple o/w/o or w/o/w emulsions. They can also be classified according to the internal phase droplet size, method of preparation, and stability into macroemulsions (globule size >400 nm) often referred to as ‘coarse’ or opaque emulsions and nanoemulsions (globule size 100-400 nm) and microemulsions (globule size 10-100 nm) which are monodisperse, transparent and thermodynamically stable mixtures of oil and water ⁽¹³⁰⁾.

Biosurfactants generally display excellent emulsifying activity, expressed by a relatively high emulsification index (E), a parameter indicating the capacity of a surfactant to produce a stable emulsion under specific conditions ⁽¹³¹⁾. The emulsification index (E24) is a commonly used parameter to characterize the surface activity of newly produced biosurfactants ^(132, 133). An aqueous biosurfactant solution is vortex-mixed with an oil and the emulsion formed is kept aside for 24 h at 25°C. E24 is calculated using the following formula:

$$E24 \% = \frac{H_{\text{emulsion}}}{H_{\text{total}}} \times 100$$

where “H” indicates the height of the layer.

The emulsifying properties of biosurfactants, particularly the anionic rhamnolipid and lipopeptide types, have been the subject of several studies involving pH conditions and different types of oil ⁽¹³⁴⁻¹³⁶⁾. Emulsification by rhamnolipid biosurfactants could be ameliorated by conjugation with whey protein ⁽¹³⁷⁾. Biosurfactants were reported as emulsifiers in the formulation of microemulsion drug delivery systems ⁽¹³⁸⁾ and for bioremediation purposes ⁽¹³⁹⁾. Rhamnolipids can form o/w nanoemulsions with different oils with good stability over a wide range of pH, temperature and ionic strength ⁽¹⁴⁰⁾. Moreover, surfactin-stabilized nanoemulsions showed prominent antimicrobial effect as a result of fusion with bacterial cell walls and viral envelopes ^(141, 142), a property of importance in the preservation of commercial products. Finally, polymeric biosurfactants such as emulsan, biodispersan, and alasan, provide great potential as bio-emulsifiers in the food, paint, bioremediation, detergent, and cosmetics industries ⁽¹⁴³⁻¹⁴⁵⁾. Bio-emulsifiers

were also shown to exhibit great antimicrobial activity ⁽¹⁴⁶⁾ which adds to their cleaning efficacy in antimicrobial household detergent and institutional cleaning.

3.5.Applications of biosurfactants

3.5.1. Industrial applications

Biosurfactants as effective, sustainable, and ecofriendly surfactants offer extraordinary benefits to many industries ⁽²²⁾. Biosurfactants are involved in an infinite number of physicochemical phenomena and industrial processes to increase wettability and solubility, remove soil, fixing dyes, producing emulsions, stabilizing dispersions, coagulating suspended solids, foaming and defoaming and much more ^(2, 3). The most significant industrial applications of biosurfactants are shown in Figure 5. These include environmental applications such as removal of environmental contaminants ⁽³⁾, oil dispersal and bioremediation ⁽¹⁴⁷⁻¹⁴⁹⁾, paints and textile industries ^(150, 151), household, industrial and institutional detergency, personal care and cosmetics industry ^(6, 152, 153), etc.

Figure 5: Environmental and industrial applications of biosurfactants ⁽³⁾

3.5.2. Biomedical applications of biosurfactants

The extensive research efforts over the last few decades highlighted the excellent prospects of biosurfactants as bioactive materials for biomedical and pharmaceutical applications. Such applications have been the subject of many excellent review articles ^(5, 154-156). Biomedical applications of biosurfactants comprise chiefly a wide range of potential therapeutic activities as

well as the development of various carrier systems for drug and gene delivery. Figure 6 summarizes some of the most promising biomedical applications of biosurfactants.

Figure 6: Biomedical applications of biosurfactants

3.5.2.1. Biosurfactants as potential therapeutic agents

3.5.2.1.1. Antimicrobial and anti-biofilm agents

Biosurfactants have antimicrobial activities whose mechanisms of action are distinct from common antimicrobial agents with known resistance profiles. Thus, biosurfactants may be good antimicrobial candidates for medical, veterinary, and agricultural purposes. In addition, antimicrobial biosurfactants may contribute to the curbing of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) because of their different antimicrobial mechanisms of action as well as the potential of reducing the level of antibiotic residues in the aquatic environment such as rivers, lakes, and drinking water, known to be a source of AMR dissemination ^(157, 158).

Biosurfactants were reported to exert antimicrobial activity by disrupting multiple aspects of cell membrane function and inhibiting the synthesis of cell membrane protein, DNA, and RNA ^(159, 160). Generally, biosurfactants exert bacteriostatic, bactericidal, anti-biofilm, biofilm disruption, as well as adjuvant and synergistic effects with antibiotics ⁽⁷⁾. Examples of biosurfactants with known antimicrobial activity include Polymyxin A (*Bacillus polymyxa*), surfactin, iturin, and Bacillomycin D (*B. subtilis*) mannosylerythritol lipids from *Candida*, rhamnolipids from *P. aeruginosa*, and biosurfactants isolated from *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* to mention a few ⁽¹⁵⁹⁾.

Biosurfactants also display anti-fungal activity and prevent the formation of fungal biofilms^(45, 161). Moreover, biosurfactants of the rhamnolipid type and other types show activity against enveloped viruses including SARS-CoV-2^(35, 162). Rhamnolipid nano-micelles proved successful as a potential hand sanitizer for the protection against COVID-19 virus⁽¹⁶³⁾.

3.5.2.1.2. Anti-cancer agents

Biosurfactants exhibit relatively high activity against several cancer types including mainly breast and lung cancer, leukemia, melanoma, colon cancer and squamous cell carcinoma⁽¹⁶⁴⁾. Multiple mechanisms have been put forward to describe the anticancer activity of biosurfactants. These comprise disruption of cancer cell membrane by lysis and increasing membrane permeability⁽¹⁶⁵⁾, delaying of cell evolution, inhibition of vital signaling pathways, induction of apoptosis by death receptors in cancer cells, stimulation of natural killer T (NKT) cells and suppression of angiogenesis. These mechanisms are illustrated in (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Mechanisms of anti-cancer activity of biosurfactants⁽⁷³⁾

Biosurfactants with reported anti-cancer activity comprise chiefly lipopeptides such as surfactin^(49, 50) and glycopeptides including mannosylerythritol lipids (MELs)⁽¹⁶⁶⁾ trehalose lipids⁽¹⁶⁷⁾, Lactonic sophorolipids^(168, 169) and rhamnolipids⁽¹⁷⁰⁾.

3.5.2.1.3. Immunomodulatory agents

Several BS are known to modulate immune responses both at cellular and humoral levels, either by suppression or activation of immune system modifying resistance to diseases. The interference

of biosurfactants of various classes including glycolipids, phospholipids and lipopeptides with the activities or mechanism of action of immune response has been reviewed recently^(171, 172).

3.5.2.1.4. Anti-inflammatory agents

Some biosurfactants have great potential as anti-inflammatory agents. For instance, surfactin has been reported to exhibit anti-inflammatory effects by attenuating the activation of nuclear factor- κ B (NF- κ B), which is involved in the nuclear factor- κ B (NF- κ B) cell signaling pathways⁽¹⁷³⁾. A recent report indicated the production of cationic proteins, reactive oxygen species (ROS) and lysozyme by biosurfactants following the inflammatory response and suggested their use for therapeutic purposes, including inflammation induced by COVID-19⁽¹⁷⁴⁾.

3.5.2.1.5. Antioxidant agents

Biosurfactants were reported to block the oxidative chain reaction flow leading to impeded increase of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive nitrogen species generated during various physiological processes, preventing oxidative stress or oxidative damage. Such antioxidant activity of biosurfactants was demonstrated to inhibit bacterial growth^(175, 176) and enhance wound healing⁽¹⁷⁷⁾.

3.5.2.2. Biosurfactants in drug delivery

The use of free therapeutic agents in conventional pharmaceutical dosage forms poses major challenges regarding efficacy and safety of drug therapy. Poor drug solubility, poor absorption and bioavailability, instability in the biological milieu, fast drug release necessitating frequent administration and non-targeted delivery leading to toxic effects on nano-target organs, and poor transport across biological barriers and intracellular delivery represent the most prominent challenges in this respect. Therefore, the use of drug delivery systems, particularly those based on nanotechnology, can greatly advance the development of more effective and safer drug formulations by addressing these critical issues⁽¹⁷⁸⁻¹⁸⁰⁾. The major types of advanced nano-scale drug delivery systems include polymeric-based nanoparticles with diverse structures and properties⁽¹⁸¹⁾, lipid-based nanocarriers such as liposomes, solid lipid nanoparticles and lipid nanocapsules⁽¹⁸²⁾, micelle-based nanocarriers embracing surfactant nanomicelles^(163, 183) and polymeric nanomicelles⁽¹⁸⁴⁾, in addition to carbon-based⁽¹⁸⁵⁾, and metal-based⁽¹⁸⁶⁾ nanocarriers.

Biosurfactants play multiple roles in nanotechnology-based drug delivery: i) They can be encapsulated as drug-like agents to enhance their bioactivity and ii) utilized in the development of nanocarriers for drug delivery either as nanocarrier-forming materials or formulation additives in addition to iii) their use as emulsifying agents in emulsion-based delivery systems.

3.5.2.2.1. Biosurfactants as encapsulated bioactive agents

It has been reported that encapsulation of biosurfactants in different types of nanocarriers led to enhanced bioactivity⁽¹⁸⁷⁾. Several studies reported the encapsulation of biosurfactants in lipid-based nanocarriers such as liposomes (phospholipid bilayers) nonionic (surfactant bilayer vesicles) as well as polymer-based nanocarriers. For example, entrapment of biosurfactants isolated from *Lactobacillus gasseri* in liposomes enhanced the antibiofilm activity against methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* strains⁽¹⁸⁸⁾. Delivery of a *Lactobacillus crispatus* BC1 biosurfactant by hyalurosomes, hyaluronan-coated liposomes also enhanced the biosurfactant efficacy against *Candida* biofilm⁽¹⁸⁹⁾. Niosomes were shown to enhance the anti-biofilm activity of a sophorolipid-

amphotericin B formulation against *Candida albicans* ⁽¹⁹⁰⁾. Regarding polymer-based nanocarriers, chitosan nanoparticles were shown to boost the antimicrobial efficacy of a rhamnolipid biosurfactant ⁽¹⁹¹⁾ and the eradication rate of *Helicobacter pylori* biofilm by a glycopeptide biosurfactant ⁽¹⁹¹⁾. Moreover, sophorolipids-loaded PEGylated poly(lactide-co-glycolide) nanocapsules were used as a new approach to target colon carcinoma in mice ⁽¹⁹²⁾.

3.5.2.2.2. Biosurfactants as drug delivery systems or components

In addition to the high potential of biosurfactants as anti-cancer therapeutic agents, these molecules can also be used as drug delivery systems or formulation additives to bioactivate the nanocarrier and improve cellular interactions. As drug delivery vehicles, biosurfactants have been investigated as self-assembly nanostructures and the formulation of other delivery systems such as liposomes and emulsion-type vehicles as summarized below.

Self-assembly formers: Spontaneous self-assembly of biosurfactants due to their amphiphilic nature results in the formation of nanostructures as potential delivery system. For instance, rhamnolipid nano-micelles proved promising as potential hand sanitizer ⁽¹⁶³⁾. Rhamnolipid self-assembly nanoparticles were also successful as a delivery system for pheophorbide, a hydrophobic photosensitizer for anti-cancer photodynamic therapy ⁽¹⁹³⁾. Surfactin micelle-like clusters increased the oral bioavailability and hypoglycemic effect of insulin ⁽⁹⁾ and ameliorated the internalization and antitumor activity of bleomycin ⁽¹¹⁾. Moreover, doxorubicin-loaded surfactin-based nanostructures allowed reversal of multidrug resistance in human breast cancer MCF-7/ADR cells (10) while its self-assembly with a gambogic acid-near-infrared dye conjugate into "mosaic-type" nanoparticles selectively targeted drug release into hypoxic cancer cells ⁽¹⁹⁴⁾.

Nanocarrier matrix: Biosurfactants have been reported as matrix formers in the formulation of bioactive nanocarriers such as liposomes, niosomes and polymer nanoparticles. For instance, rhamnolipid-based liposomes proved promising as a nanocarrier for enhancing the antibacterial activity of natural peptides ⁽¹⁹⁵⁾. Novel biosurfactant-based mixed vesicles containing lactobacilli biosurfactant for vaginal delivery increased the anti-candida drug activity ⁽¹⁹⁶⁾. Sophorolipids-based niosomes were also promising for the delivery of amphotericin B (AmB) against *C. albicans* ⁽¹⁹⁰⁾. As nanoparticles, emulsan was used to formulate core-shell nanoparticles for delivery of pheophorbide for anti-cancer photodynamic therapy ⁽¹⁹⁷⁾.

3.5.2.2.3. Biosurfactants as formulation additives

Biosurfactants have also been investigated as bioactive formulation additives to functionalize different drug carriers. For example, coating nanoparticles with a biosurfactant enhanced efficient delivery of a doxorubicin/erlotinib anti-cancer combination to cancer cells ⁽¹⁹⁸⁾ and the oral delivery of curcumin ⁽¹⁹⁹⁾. Incorporation of a mannosylerythritol lipid-A (MEL-A) biosurfactant in liposomes enhanced the activity of the anticancer betulinic acid and the pharmaceutical attributes of liposomes ⁽²⁰⁰⁾. Inclusion of surfactin in cationic liposomes and enteric-coated microparticles enhanced the cellular delivery of siRNA ⁽²⁰¹⁾ and the hypoglycemic effect of insulin respectively ^(201, 202). Moreover, addition of surfactin to lipid nanocapsules was reported recently to improve the anticancer activity of encapsulated itraconazole, an antifungal drug with repurposing potential ⁽²⁰³⁾.

3.5.2.2.4. Biosurfactants as emulsifiers

Biosurfactants have a well-established emulsification role in the development of conventional o/w emulsions⁽⁴⁴⁾ and microemulsion-based delivery systems⁽²⁰⁴⁾. Biosurfactants can also be used for the formation and stabilization of nanoemulsions for external use⁽²⁰⁵⁻²⁰⁷⁾. According to Lewinska et al.⁽²⁰⁸⁾, a self-emulsifying delivery system (isotropic mixture of oils, surfactants, solvents and co-solvents) increased the transport of active substances, vitamin C or vitamin E and curcumin deep into the skin. Moreover, a cream formulation of a hybrid of levan nanoparticles and a surfactin-stabilized nanoemulsion was demonstrated by different test parameters to improve the skin condition in 50% of a panel of volunteers⁽²⁰⁹⁾.

4. The key study materials

As obvious from the literature review, biosurfactants are offering great promise as sustainable and ecofriendly microbially-derived byproducts of multiple benefits in biomedical applications. The utilization of biosurfactants in drug delivery applications both as potential bioactive drug-like agents and as drug carriers or components thereof has attracted growing research attention over the last few years. However, this field is still in its infancy and the discovery of more biosurfactants as well as exploration of their aptitude in drug delivery will add value to the pharmaceutical application of biosurfactants. The present thesis involves the production of a lipopeptide biosurfactant (LBS) using a new microbial producer, the bacillus strain, *Bacillus licheniformis* (*B. licheniformis*) SHG10 DSMZ28096, and to explore its potential in drug delivery. *B. licheniformis* is a Gram-positive spore-forming bacterial species of high biotechnological interest with numerous present and potential uses ⁽²¹⁰⁾.

4.1. Lipopeptide biosurfactants

Lipopeptide biosurfactants (LBSs) are produced by fungi and various bacterial genera such as *Streptomyces*, *Pseudomonas* and *Bacillus*. LBSs are composed of a lipid tail linked to a short linear or cyclic oligopeptide (Figure 8). LBSs from *Bacillus* are classified in three families of cyclic compounds: surfactin, iturin and Fengycin. Each family contains variants with the same peptide length but with different residues at specific positions. The surfactin family encompasses different heptapeptide variants including the esperin, lichenysin, pumilacidin and surfactin groups. The peptide moiety is linked to a β -hydroxyl fatty acid ⁽²¹¹⁾.

Figure 8 : The lipopeptide cyclic heptapeptide biosurfactants, lichenysin and surfactin ⁽¹⁾

LBSs were selected for the study as the most interesting group of biosurfactants. Their structural diversity, surface activity and multiple biological functionalities endowed them with pharmaceutical characteristics as bioactive agents and drug carriers. As drug-like agents, LBS were incorporated in nanof formulations such as nanoparticles ^(212, 213) and nanofibers ^(214, 215) for sustained delivery antimicrobial applications.

LBSs also play multiple roles in the development of nanof formulations ⁽²¹⁶⁾. These involve mainly emulsification, inherent self-assembly into nano-sized drug delivery systems, and bestowing of bioactivity to polymer-based or lipid-based drug delivery systems. In fact, SF easily self-assemble into sphere-like nanostructures even at low concentration ⁽²¹⁷⁾ which were shown to improve the biological performance of entrapped therapeutic agents. For instance, surfactin

micelle-like clusters were shown to ameliorate the anticancer activity of bleomycin⁽¹¹⁾ and doxorubicin⁽¹⁰⁾ and targeting drug release into hypoxic cancer cells⁽¹⁹⁴⁾.

As functional formulation ingredient, the LBS surfactin has a well-documented role in the development of emulsions⁽⁴⁴⁾, microemulsions⁽²⁰⁴⁾ and nanoemulsions^(208, 209). Moreover, addition of SF to lipid nanocapsules was reported to improve the anticancer activity of encapsulated itraconazole, an antifungal drug with repurposing potential for cancer treatment⁽²⁰³⁾.

The LBS produced by *B. licheniformis* SHG10 DSMZ28096 is intended to be used in the form of nano-self assemblies as a drug nanocarrier for potential anti-cancer applications.

4.2. Prodigiosin

To date, drug delivery applications involving LBSs including surfactin as a drug-like agent or formulation ingredient have been generally restricted to synthetic drugs^(10, 11, 194). We herein propose a nanoformulation combining prodigiosin (PG), a secondary bacterial metabolite, incorporated in LBS-nano self-assemblies (nSAs) as a potential nanobiotechnology-based biotherapeutic.

PG, a heterocyclic bacterial secondary metabolite belonging to the class of tripyrrole compounds (Figure 9), is synthesized by a number of different Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacterial strains, mainly *Serratia marcescens* (*S. marcescens*)⁽²¹⁸⁾. PG is a highly lipophilic vibrant red color pigment with a Log POW of 5.16⁽²¹⁹⁾.

Figure 9: Chemical structure of prodigiosin

PG has been the subject of intense research over the last decade for its ability to induce apoptosis in a wide range of cancer cell lines, including hematopoietic cancer, breast cancer, gastric cancer, colon cancer, lung cancer, and rat hepatocellular carcinoma cell lines, with no marked toxicity in nonmalignant cells and to exert antimicrobial actions⁽²²⁰⁾. However, the use of PG as bioactive agent drug in pharmaceutical formulations is highly challenged by its poor solubility. Most potential drug delivery applications have been based on carrier systems such as microparticles⁽²²¹⁾, nanoparticles⁽²²²⁻²²⁴⁾, nanomicelles⁽²²⁵⁾, liposomes⁽²²⁶⁾, hydrogels⁽²²⁷⁾, nanofibers^(228, 229), polymer scaffolds⁽²³⁰⁾. Nanomicelles of synthetic surfactants such as Tween 80 have been used

as carrier systems for PG but for biotechnological applications, particularly the extraction of PG from *S. marcescens* culture and the dyeing of textiles^(231, 232).

It is worth noting that reports on combinatorial systems involving PG and biosurfactants are scarce and restricted to antibacterial activity to date^(218, 233). To the best of our knowledge, a combinatorial anticancer delivery system including nano-self-assemblies (nSAs) of a biosurfactant as a nanocarrier for PG has not been reported so far. This initiated the development of PG-loaded LBS nSAs as a bioinspired combinatorial delivery aiming at enhancing the solubility and anti-cancer activity of PG.

5. MATERIALS AND METHODS

5.1. MATERIALS

5.1.1. Chemicals

Chloroform, hydrochloric acid and glucose (Pioneers for chemicals (PIOCHEM), Egypt). EDTA, di-sodium phosphate, calcium chloride, ferrous sulphate and ammonium nitrate (CHEMINJECT, Ireland). Manganese sulphate and dimethyl sulfoxide (Riedel-de Haën, Germany). Petroleum ether (60-80°C) and magnesium sulphate (ADWIC, Egypt). Yeast extract (Lab M company, UK). Sodium hydroxide, tryptone and glacial acetic acid 99.5% extra pure (LOBA CHEMIE Pvt Ltd, India). Resazurin sodium salt powder (Sigma-Aldrich). Methanol HPLC (Fisher Scientific, UK) and ethyl alcohol (The International Company for Sup. & Med. Industries, Egypt). Ammonium acetate (WINLAB, India). All other reagents and chemicals are of analytical grade.

5.1.2. Bacterial strains

Bacillus licheniformis SHG10 DSMZ28096 (*B. licheniformis*) previously submitted in the GenBank under the accession number: JN853580.1. and *Serratia marcescens* (*S. marcescens*) were used for the production of lipopeptide biosurfactant (LBS) and prodigiosin (PG), respectively. Both strains were obtained from the culture collection of the Microbial Biotechnology Laboratory, Biotechnology Department, Institute of Graduate Studies and Research, Alexandria University. Bacterial strains used in the antibacterial activity study included three multidrug resistant (MDR) strains, namely *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli* ATCC25922 and *E. coli* ATCC35218), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (*P. aeruginosa* ATCC27853) in addition to a standard *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) strain. All strains were clinical isolates obtained from the microbiological laboratory, Faculty of Medicine, Alexandria University.

5.1.3. Culture media

Liquid broth or nutrient broth (NB) and liquid broth agar or nutrient agar (NA) were used during the course of activation and preparation of a seed culture from *B. licheniformis* and *S. marcescens*. Nutrient agar and nutrient broth were used in the course of activation and culturing of bacterial strains in the antibacterial activity study. Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM) from GIBCO, Thermofisher Scientific, was used as the cell culture medium for cytotoxicity assay. The chemical composition of culture media and lipopeptide biosurfactant and prodigiosin production media (BPM) used in the study is detailed below:

Liquid broth media or Nutrient broth (NB)

Tryptone	10 g/L
Yeast extract	5 g/L
Sodium chloride	10 g/L

*Liquid broth agar media or Nutrient agar (NA) have the same composition of liquid broth or NB in addition to nutrient agar (15g/L)

Lipopetide biosurfactant production medium (BPM)

Glucose	20.0 g /L
Dihydrogen potassium phosphate	4.08 g/L
Ammonium nitrate	4.0 g /L
Magnesium sulphate	0.2 g /L
Disodium phosphate	7.12 g /L
Mangan sulphate	0.00067 g /L
EDTA	0.00148 g /L
Calcium chloride	0.00077 g /L
Ferrous Sulfate	0.0011 g/L

Prodigiosin production medium (peanut based-distilled water)

Peanut powder	20 g/L
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Cell lines

MDA-MB-231 and MCF-7 breast cancer cell lines were purchased from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC, USA).

5.2.METHODS

5.2.1. Production and extraction of *Bacillus licheniformis* lipopeptide biosurfactant

An overnight single colony of *B. licheniformis* SHG10 DSMZ28096 was used to inoculate 50 mL liquid broth media in 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask. The inoculated broth was incubated for 24 h at 37°C with agitation at 150 rpm using a New Brunswick Incubator Shaker, USA. A 3 mL-aliquot of the overnight seed culture was used to inoculate 50 mL the LBS production medium (BPM) in 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask. The inoculated medium was incubated for 24 h at 40°C with agitation at 150 rpm. This was followed by collection of the bacterial cells by centrifugation of the culture at 7000 rpm for 10 min. The produced lipopeptide biosurfactant (LBS) was isolated as reported⁽²³⁴⁾. Briefly, the cell free-supernatant was mixed with concentrated HCl at pH 2.0 to precipitate the LBS. This was followed by incubation overnight at 4°C. The jelly-like slurry was collected by centrifugation at 7000 rpm for 5 min and washed several times with alkaline water, pH 8.0 to for neutralization. The extracted crude LBS was allowed to dry in the oven at 40°C for one week. The dried LBS powder was subjected to solvent extraction with a chloroform: methanol mixture (2:1) at room temperature. After solvent removal, a viscous honey-colored crude LBS mass was obtained as reported⁽²³⁵⁾.

The extracted crude LBS was subjected to partial purification using a solid phase extraction (SPE) method⁽²³⁶⁾. The SPE cartridges (Teknokroma™ Finisterre™ SPE columns C18 / 17%, 500 mg /6 mL) were conditioned with 5 mL distilled water before loading with 5 ml of the LBS. Extraction was performed firstly by gravity and or by pressure using syringe plunger. The cartridges were then washed with 5 mL methanol then dried after each washing step. The partially purified LBS was eluted using 5 mL of a chloroform: methanol solvent mixture (2: 1). The LBS solution was dried in the oven for 24 h at 37°C. The viscous honey-colored LBS paste obtained was kept in a glass container protected from light in the refrigerator (4°C).

5.2.2. Characterization of *B. licheniformis* lipopeptide biosurfactant (LBS)

5.2.2.1. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

The FTIR spectrum of the partially purified LBS was recorded using the KBr pellet method and a Fourier Transform Spectrophotometer (Perkin Elmer FT-IR Spectrometer, Spectrum BX, USA) within the range 4500–450 cm⁻¹.

5.2.2.2. Gas Chromatography (GC)

The partially purified LBS was subjected to gas chromatography (GC) using a Hewlett Packard 6890 Gas Chromatograph. For lipid extraction from sample, 400mg from purified BS was weighted into 250ml centrifuge bottle then sufficient water was added to bring total water present to 16 ml together with 40ml methanol and 20ml chloroform. After maceration for 2min, further 20ml chloroform was added and the mixture was macerated again for 30 Sec then 20ml water was added with maceration for 30 sec. Lipids were separated by centrifugation at 2500 rpm for 10 min, lower chloroform layer was collected and filtered by a coarse filter paper then chloroform was dried. For methylation step, 50mg from extracted lipids weighted in a tube with 5 ml of methanolic sulphuric acid and 2 ml of benzene the tube was placed in water bath at 90°C for an hour and half then it was cooled. For separation, 8 ml of water and 5 ml petroleum ether was added and shaken strongly. Finally petroleum ether layer was separated out and dried off. A silica capillary column HP-INWAX (Crosslinked polyethylene glycol, 60 m, 0.25 mm ID and 0.25µm film thickness) was used. Analysis was performed as reported⁽²³⁷⁾.

5.2.2.3. Stability profiling of the crude lipopeptide biosurfactant (LBS)

The effect of temperature and pH on the stability of the crude LBS was assessed by determining its emulsifying efficiency expressed as the emulsifying index at 24 h (E24) as reported⁽¹³⁶⁾. In brief, 6 mL of the cell-free LBS supernatant was vortex-mixed with 2 mL of watercrude oil in a test tube for 30 min. The mixture was then kept undisturbed for 24 h and the volume of the emulsified layer relative to the total volume of the aqueous and oil layers was measured and E24 determined using the following equation:

$$E24 \% = \frac{\text{High of emulsified layer}}{\text{High of the two components layers}} \times 100$$

To assess the effect of temperature on the E24, emulsification was performed at temperatures ranging from 4°C to 80°C (at pH=7). For the effect of pH, the LBS supernatant was acidified with 6N HCl or alkalized with 1N NaOH to adjust the pH within the range 2-12 (at RT) prior to emulsification.

5.2.3. Production and characterization of prodigiosin

5.2.3.1. Production of prodigiosin

Prodigiosin (PG) red pigment was produced from *S. marcescens* according to a reported procedure⁽²³⁸⁾. Briefly, an overnight single colony of *S. marcescens* was used to inoculate 20 mL of NB medium in a 100 mL Erlenmeyer flask. The inoculated broth was incubated at 37°C for 24 h with agitation at 150 rpm. A 5-mL aliquot of the overnight seed culture was used to inoculate 100 mL of PG production medium (peanut based-distilled water) in 1L Erlenmeyer flask⁽²³⁹⁾. The inoculated PG production medium was incubated at 28°C for 48 h with agitation at 150 rpm.

PG was extracted from the *S. marcescens* culture as reported earlier⁽²³⁸⁾. Briefly, 10% w/v NaOH was added to a *S. marcescens* culture with constant agitation at 150 rpm for 2 h. An equal volume of absolute ethanol was then added to the mixture followed by the addition of an equal volume of light petroleum ether (boiling point 40-60°C). The mixture was stirred vigorously and the petroleum ether phase containing PG was separated using a separatory funnel. The aqueous phase was re-extracted three times with the same volume of light petroleum ether. The combined petroleum ether layers from all extractions were pooled. The residual ethanol from the pooled petroleum ether layers was removed by recurrent washing with distilled water. The volume of petroleum ether was decreased by keeping it at its boiling temperature (60°C) and complete removal was accomplished by air-drying at 25°C as described⁽²⁴⁰⁾. The crude PG red precipitate was re-dissolved in 5 to 10 mL of methanol, followed by pH adjustment with 1N HCl till neutrality (pink) and subjected to partial purification by SPE method. PG was dried in the oven at 37°C till almost complete solvent evaporation and kept at -20°C in a dark bottle.

5.2.3.2. Characterization of prodigiosin

5.2.3.3. Ultraviolet-Visible (UV/VIS) spectrophotometry

The absorption spectrum of PG was recorded using a Single Beam UV-Visible Spectrophotometer (Helios Alpha, Germany). An aliquot of 100 µL methanolic PG extract was diluted 10-fold and the absorbance spectrum was recorded within the range of 400 to 600 nm against methanol as blank.

5.2.3.4. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

FTIR scans of PG in comparison to reported PG were obtained using PerkinElmer FT-IR Spectrometer. One drop of the liquid test samples, PG solution in methanol (1mg/mL), LBS dispersion in deionized water (1mg/mL) and a mixture of PG and LBS in a 1: 1 ratio on a NaCl cell. Scans were obtained in the range 4,000 to 400 cm⁻¹.

5.2.3.5. Liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS-MS)

The isolated PG was dissolved in methanol and analyzed by LC-MS-MS using UPLC-MS\MS Sciex QTRAP 5500 according to a reported method with slight modification⁽²³³⁾. An Eclipse XDB-C18 reverse phase column (4.6 x 100 mm x 3.5 µm) was used with 0% to 100% linear solvent gradient over 45 min. The eluting solvent consisted of an aqueous phase (deionized water and 0.2% acetic acid) and an organic phase (methanol and 0.2% acetic acid). PG was detected by electrospray ionization mass spectrometry (ESI-MS). High-resolution ESI-MS spectra were recorded in the m/z range 50-1000 in the positive ion mode⁽²⁴¹⁾.

5.2.4. Preparation and characterization of prodigiosin-lipopeptide biosurfactant nano-self-assemblies (PG-LBS nSAs)

5.2.4.1. Solubility of prodigiosin in lipopeptide biosurfactant (LBS) solutions

The equilibrium solubility of PG in a series of LBS solutions with increasing concentrations (100 – 800 µg/mL) was determined by vortex mixing mixtures of an excess amount of PG with the LBS solutions in deionized water for 10 min and subsequent equilibration at ambient temperature (~25°C) for one hour. The undissolved PG was separated by centrifugation and the solubilized PG was determined by UV-VIS spectrophotometry at λ_{max} 538 nm using a linear regression equation⁽²⁴²⁾. A stock standard solution of PG (2 mg/mL) was prepared by dissolving an accurately weighed amount (20 mg) of PG in 10 mL of methanol. Working solutions of PG over the range of 150-450 µg/mL were then prepared by subsequent dilution and a calibration curve (absorbance vs drug concentration) was constructed.

5.2.4.2. Prodigiosin assay validation

The UV assay was validated according to the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines⁽²⁴³⁾. The method validation for the three calibration curves used was carried out regarding the following parameters: linearity, intraday precision, accuracy and reproducibility.

Linearity and range

Eight solutions of different concentrations were prepared using a PG standard stock solution (150-450 µg/mL). Data collected was then fitted into a calibration plot and linearity was evaluated by determination of the correlation coefficient (R^2)

Accuracy

Accuracy is the closeness of the data obtained experimentally to the true value. A recovery study was carried out using the same set of concentrations applied for calibration curve. The concentration of PG in the standard solutions was compared to the calculated concentration from the corresponding calibration curve.

Inter-day precision

Inter-day precision were evaluated by measuring the same set of concentrations three times on three different days. The concentrations found by refitting the absorbance values obtained from the standard serial dilutions into the calibration equation were calculated. Their mean value, standard deviation (SD) and the coefficient of variation (CV %) were calculated.

Reproducibility

Reproducibility of PG standard calibration curve was carried out by comparing the absorbance of different sets of standard calibration curves performed on different days.

5.2.4.3. Preparation of prodigiosin (PG)-lipopeptide biosurfactant (LBS) nano-self-assemblies (PG-LBS nSAs)

PG-LBS nano-self-assemblies were prepared using a two-step method (method A1-3) which involved the formation of LBS self-assemblies (Step 1) followed by PG loading (Step 2) and a one-step method (Method B) which featured simultaneous self-assembly of BS and PG loading. These methods were described in the Methods section (Table 4).

Method A1: LBS nSAs were prepared by vortex mixing of a 1mg/mL LBS solution (10 mL). A known amount of PG (30 mg) was incorporated into the formed LBS-nSAs by sonication for 30 min at room temperature ⁽²⁴⁴⁾.

Method A2: This method was similar to method A1 except that the LBS solution (5mg/5mL) was vortexed for 5 min and PG (15mg) was incorporated into LBS nSAs by sonication for 30 min at 50°C ⁽²⁴⁵⁾.

Method A3: LBS nSAs were prepared by sonication of a 10mg/10mL solution of LBS at 50°C for 30 min. PG (30 mg) was incorporated into 5 mL of the dispersion of LBS nSAs by sonication for 30 min at 50°C ⁽²⁴⁴⁾.

Method B: PG-loaded LBS nSAs were prepared in one step by sonicating a mixture of LBS (10 mg) and PG (30 mg) in 10 ml of deionized water for 30 min at 50°C ⁽²⁴⁶⁾.

The loading procedures in both methods are listed in (Table 4). In all procedures, undissolved PG was separated by filtration through Whatman No 1 filter paper.

Table 4: Methods of preparation of PG-loaded LBS nano-self assemblies (LBS nSAs)

Method A (Two step-method)		
Preparation of LBS nSAs		PG loading into LBS nSAs
Method A1	Vortexed at RT for 15 min	Sonication for 30 min at RT
Method A2	Vortexed at RT for 5 min	Sonication for 30 min at 50°C
Method A3	Sonicated at 50°C for 30 min	Sonication for 30 min at 50°C
Method B (One step-method)		
Sonication of a mixture of LBS (10 mg) and PG (30 mg) in 10 mL deionized water for 30 min at 50°C		

The physical stability of freshly prepared PG-LBS nSAs assessed during 14 days at 4°C regarding phase separation or discoloration was used as a criterion for formulation selection.

5.2.4.4. Characterization of prodigiosin-biosurfactant nano-self-assemblies

5.2.4.4.1. Drug content and entrapment efficiency (EE%)

PG content in PG-LBS nSAs was determined by dissolving 100 μ L PG-LBS nSAs in methanol. The amount of PG in 20-fold diluted methanol solution was then determined by UV-VIS spectrophotometry at λ_{max} 538 nm. PG entrapment efficiency (EE%) and loading capacity (LC%) were then calculated using the following formulas ⁽²⁴⁷⁾:

$$\text{EE \%} = \frac{\text{Drug content (mg)}}{\text{Initial drug amount (mg)}} \times 100$$

$$\text{LC \%} = \frac{\text{Drug content(mg)}}{\text{Drug content PG (mg)+ Dry weight of LBS(mg)}} \times 100$$

Where, total dry weight of PG-LBS nSAs is the sum of calculated PG content and the initial weight of LBS forming the nSAs without the water content.

According to the results of drug content and EE%, a selected PG-LBS nSAs formula was further tested for color stability away from light at 4°C, for 14 days. A PG methanolic solution (1 mg/mL) in HPLC grade methanol was used as control. PG content in the test samples was analyzed spectrophotometrically at λ_{max} 538 nm at different time intervals (0, 2, 4, 7 and 14 days). Residual PG concentration was calculated.

5.2.4.4.2. Morphology by transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

The morphology of the selected PG-LBs nSAs and the corresponding blank LBs nSAs was examined using a JSM-1400 PLUS Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM). The dispersions were diluted 1 in 30 with deionized water after filtration using Whatman filter paper. The diluted samples were sonicated for 5 min. One drop of the dispersion was placed on copper grids and the excess removed with a filter paper. The sample was negatively stained using 70% uranyl acetate solution for 30 sec followed by air-drying. The images were picked at 50000x magnification power and 80. KV.

5.2.4.4.3. Colloidal properties

The mean hydrodynamic radius, polydispersity index (PDI), and ζ -potential of selected blank and PG-LBS nSAs were measured using Malvern Zetasizer Nano ZS90 (Malvern Instruments) at a fixed angle (173°) at 25°C and a 4mW He-Ne laser at wavelength of 633 nm and laser power of 4 mW at 25°C (Zetasizer® Nano ZS series DTS 1060, Malvern Instruments S.A, Worcestershire, UK) after suitable dilution. The ζ -potential was determined at 25°C in water (dielectric constant 79, refractive index 1.33, viscosity 0.89 cP) using a cell voltage of 150 V and 5 mA current.

5.2.4.4.4. Thermal analysis

Thermal analysis of the selected samples was performed using TGA Instruments SDT 2960 Simultaneous DTA-TGA Thermal Analyzer which measures both endothermic or exothermic changes (DTA) as well as weight changes (TGA) associated with transitions in the sample as a function of temperature and time in a controlled atmosphere. Samples were heated at rate of 10°C.min⁻¹ in an air atmosphere over the temperature range 40 to 700°C.

5.2.5. Biological activity

5.2.5.1. Hemolytic activity

The *in vitro* hemolytic activity of blank LBS nSAs was assessed using fresh human blood as reported ⁽²⁴⁸⁾. In brief, a 2 mL blood sample, collected from a healthy young volunteer under medical supervision, was mixed with EDTA and centrifuged at 2500 rpm for 10 min. Red blood cells (RBCs) were washed three times with PBS pH 7.4 and diluted to a 50% suspension with the same buffer. A 50 μ L sample of the RBCs suspension was added to 950 μ L of LBS dispersion to prepare final LBS concentrations (100 - 700 μ g/mL). Triton X-100 (0.1% v/v in deionized water and PBS were used as the positive and negative control, respectively. All samples were incubated in a shaking water bath at 200 rpm and 37°C for 30 min. Intact erythrocytes were isolated by centrifugation at 10000 rpm for 5 min. The absorbance (A) of the supernatant was measured at 540 nm. The percentage hemolysis was calculated using the following formula:

$$\% \text{ Hemolysis} = \frac{A_{\text{Sample}} - A_{\text{Negative control}}}{A_{\text{Positive control}} - A_{\text{Negative control}}} \times 100$$

5.2.5.2. Antibacterial activity

The antibacterial activity of PG, blank LBS nSAs and PG-LBS nSAs against three MDR bacterial strains, namely *E. coli* ATCC25922, *E. coli* ATCC35218, and *P. aeruginosa* and a standard *S. aureus* strain was assessed by determining the minimum inhibitory concentration, MIC in μ g/mL using the standard broth microdilution method ⁽²⁴⁹⁾. A resazurin solution 15 mg/100 mL was prepared in deionized water, filtered using a Millipore membrane filter (0.22 μ m) and kept at 4°C. Briefly, 50 μ L of nutrient broth was added to 12 wells of a 96-well round bottom microtiter plate (from well 1 to well 12). A 50 μ L aliquot of 5% PG solution in DMSO was added to well 1. Ten serial PG dilutions (well 1 to well 10) were obtained by diluting 50 μ L of the PG solution in each well with nutrient agar in the next well. A 50 μ L of bacterial inoculum from a test strain (equals 0.5 MacFarland) was added to the wells 1 to 11 and the procedure repeated for the three other strains. Antibacterial assessment was performed in duplicate. All cultures were incubated at 37°C for 24 h. The next day, 30 μ L of resazurin solution (0.015% w/v) was added to each well. In all microtitre plates, well 11 and well 12 were used as positive and negative controls, respectively. The microtitre plates were incubated in the dark for 4 h at room temperature. The negative control wells had a blue color. The change in color of resazurin dye in the wells was indicative of antibacterial activity as follows: bacterial growth (pink color), bacterial growth inhibition (purple color). A weak or strong purple color was indicative of weak bacterial growth inhibition and strong bacterial growth inhibition respectively. The MIC of the text samples was determined as the lowest concentration of the sample at which the growth of the bacterial strains was inhibited ⁽²⁵⁰⁾.

5.2.5.3. Anti-cancer activity

The anticancer activity of PG-LBS nSAs in comparison with PG, LBS, and LBS nSAs was assessed at different concentrations using human breast adenocarcinoma MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 cell lines following 24 h and 48 h contact with the cancer cells at 37°C. The concentration range for either PG or PG-LBS nSAs was 3.12 - 100 µg/mL while for LBS and LBS nSAs, it was 0.81-25 µg/mL. Cell viability was assessed in duplicate using the MTT assay as reported earlier⁽²⁵¹⁾. Stock solutions of and PG (5mg/mL) and LBS (1mg/mL) were prepared in DMSO and those of LBS nSAs and PG-LBS nSAs were prepared in deionized water. All test formulations were prepared under aseptic conditions. Cells were maintained in Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM) containing 10% FBS in a CO₂ incubator (5% CO₂ at 37°C) and were seeded (4.0×10³/well) in a 96-well plate containing 100 µL of DMEM for 24 h for cell attachment. The culture medium was replaced with 100µL of a fresh medium containing the samples and incubated for another 24 h and 48 h. The culture medium was replaced with 100 µL MTT solution (0.5mg/mL in DMEM) and incubated in the dark for 4 h at 37°C. After removing the supernatant by centrifugation at 2000 rpm for 10 min, MTT-formazan crystals in the wells were dissolved with 100 µL of DMSO by agitation for 15 min. Absorbance was measured at 570 nm using a microplate reader (Model 550, Bio-Rad, USA). Origin 8.0 software (Origin Lab, Northampton, MA) was used to calculate IC₅₀ values. Dose response curves were plotted after correction by subtracting the background absorbance from the controls. The cell viability (%) was calculated relative to the untreated control cells as follows:

$$\% \text{ Cell viability} = \frac{A}{A_c} \times 100$$

where, A is the absorbance of the treated wells and A_c is the absorbance of control wells. The median inhibitory concentrations (IC₅₀) were determined using CompuSyn software (CompuSyn, Inc., version 1) according to the Chou-Talalay method⁽²⁵²⁾. The software was used to calculate the Dose Reduction Index (DRI).

5.2.5.4. Statistical analysis

Data are shown as mean ± SD are representative of at least two measurements using Minitab ver. 17 software. IC₅₀ values were calculated by non-linear regression analysis of cell viability data. The differences between multiple groups were assessed by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Dunnett's test. A value of *p*<0.05 was indicative of significance.

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

6.1. Production and characterization of *Bacillus licheniformis* biosurfactant

6.1.1. Production of partially purified biosurfactant

Crude biosurfactant was produced by *B. licheniformis* SHG10 DSMZ28096 using 1.5 L production medium dispensed as 50 mL portions in 250 mL Erlenmeyer flasks (Figure 10). The biosurfactant yield was almost 5.0 g after acid precipitation (Figure 11a). This was calculated following drying of the jelly-like crude product (Figure 11b) at 37°C in the oven for one week.

Figure 10: Production of biosurfactant from *B. licheniformis* SHG10 DSMZ28096 in production medium dispensed in 250 mL Erlenmeyer flasks.

Figure 11: Extraction of the crude biosurfactant of *B. licheniformis* SHG10 DSMZ28096 (a) The acid-precipitated biosurfactant and (b) the jelly-like crude biosurfactant before drying in the oven.

The crude jelly-like crude biosurfactant (5g approximately) was subjected to a liquid–liquid extraction method using methanol: chloroform (1:2) prior to loading onto the solid-phase extraction (SPE) cartridge. After liquid-liquid extraction of the dried biosurfactant, 5.0 mL of the eluted biosurfactant was obtained from the SPE cartridge. This was dried in the oven at 37°C for

2 days to yield 85 ± 10 mg of partially purified biosurfactant which was kept at 4°C pending use. This was designated as BS.

6.1.2. Structural characterization of biosurfactant of *B. licheniformis*

6.1.2.1. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) spectra

The FTIR spectra of crude BS are shown in Figure 12A. The FTIR spectrum of the partially purified BS is shown in Figure 12B. An almost quite typical FTIR profile for the cyclic lipopeptides like surfactin and lichenysin produced by bacilli as reported by other researchers⁽²⁵³⁾ was obtained. For the crude BS (Figure 12A), the peptide chain N-H was visualized at 3422 cm^{-1} and the aliphatic $\text{CH}_3\text{-CH}_2$ was obtained at 2928 cm^{-1} and 1402 cm^{-1} . However, the CO-N group for the crude BS was obtained at 1650 cm^{-1} . On the other hand, the purified BS (Figure 12B) showed FTIR pattern similar to that of surfactin with slight modifications. For the purified BS, the peptide chain N-H, the aliphatic $\text{CH}_3\text{-CH}_2$, and the CO-N groups were visualized at 3456 cm^{-1} , 2059 cm^{-1} , and 1642 cm^{-1} (Table 5).

Figure 12: FTIR spectra of (A) crude biosurfactant and (B) purified biosurfactant

Table 5: functional groups and wave numbers (cm⁻¹) of crude biosurfactant produced by *B. licheniformis* in comparison with standard surfactin⁽²⁵³⁾

Wave number (cm ⁻¹)		Functional group	Stretching mode	References
Crude biosurfactant By <i>B. licheniformis</i>	Standard surfactin⁽²⁵³⁾			
3422	3316	Peptide chain (N-H group)	(3313-3428)	(254); (255)
2928	2924	Aliphatic chain (CH3-CH2)	(2924-2929)	(256)
1650	1650	CO-N group	(1650-1652)	(257)
1402	1468	Aliphatic chain (CH3-CH2)	(1370-1469)	(258); (257)

6.1.2.2. Gas chromatography analysis

The GC profile of the partially purified BS indicated the presence of 21 lipid-based components with biosurfactant properties. The major peaks at retention times 14.19 and 17.51 min were confirmed as palmitic acid (hexadecanoic acid, C₁₆H₃₂O₂) and oleic acid (C₁₈H₃₄O₂). Other fatty acids were identified as in Table 6. The highest and lowest peak area % was for hexadecanoic acid (12.41%) and caproic acid (0.38%) respectively at 3.9 min retention time. Analysis showed similarity with a cyclic hexalipo peptide with the main fatty acids 3-hydroxylated terta, penta, hexa, and octadecanoic acids (Table 6).

Table 6: Fatty acid components of the partially purified biosurfactant

No	Fatty acid	Retention time	Peak area % (<i>B. licheniformis</i> biosurfactant)	Peak area % (Lipopeptide biosurfactant)*
1	Caproic acid	3.90	0.389	-
2	Lauric acid	9.05	8.45	-
3	Tridecanoic acid	10.5	4.30	-
4	Myristic acid	11.90	3.92	2.91
5	Myrestoeleic acid	12.23	8.5	2.132
6	Pentadecanoic acid	13.46	4.31	4.74
7	Palmitic acid	14.19	12.41	21.76
8	Pamitoleic acid	14.63	3.77	4.17
9	Heptadecanoic acid	15.43	4.08	-
10	Cis -10 heptadecanoic	15.87	4	-
11	Stearic acid	17.20	8.03	5.87
12	Oleic acid	17.51	11.88	-
13	Linoleic acid	18.26	1.56	-
14	Linolenic acid	19.90	6.69	-
15	Arachidic acid	20.42	3.58	-
16	Cis-11ecosenoic acid	21.07	0.35	13.6
17	Cis-11-14-ecosenoic acid	21.73	2.82	-
18	Cis 11-14-17- eicosatrienoic acid	23.40	5.1	-
19	Arachidonic acid	24.25	2.9	-
20	Behenic acid	25.31	0.57	-
21	Erucic acid	25.70	2.39	-

*Partially purified lipopeptide biosurfactant produced from *B. licheniformis* VS16 ⁽²⁵⁹⁾

Based on preparation conditions (precipitation of crude BS by acids) and analysis by different methods, the biosurfactant produced by *B. licheniformis* SHG10 DSMZ28096 was most probably a partially purified anionic lipopeptide. It was designated as LBS.

6.1.2.3. Stability profiling of biosurfactant at different temperatures and pH

The stability profile of crude BS was expressed as the emulsifying index at 24 h (E24) at various temperatures and pH levels as reported ⁽¹³⁶⁾. Figure 13 depicts the phase separation of the crude BS-stabilized emulsion upon changing pH and temperature.

The E24 values determined at different pH and temperature are listed in Tables 7 and 8 respectively. After being exposed to high temperatures and high alkalinity, E24 % of BS was increased while at 4°C and a neutral pH, the crude BS displayed better emulsification properties.

Figure 13: Emulsification index (E24) of Biosurfactant: (A) at pH 2.0, 7.0 and 11.0 and (B) under different temperature conditions.

Table 7: Emulsification index (E24) of the crude biosurfactant at different pH values

pH	E24
2.0	30.76
7.0	38.76
11.0	0.0

Table 8: Emulsification index (E24) of the crude biosurfactant under different temperature conditions.

Temperature	E24
4°C	50
RT	25
37°C	41.6
80°C	33.3

Physicochemical characterization data indicated that the biosurfactant produced by *B. licheniformis* SHG10 DSMZ28096 in the present study was of the lipopeptide type and was designated as lipopeptide biosurfactant (LBS) in the following sections. As this is the first time this *Bacillus* strain is used for the production of lipopeptide biosurfactants, results obtained add to the knowledge in the field.

6.2. Production and characterization of prodigiosin by *Serratia marcescens*

6.2.1. Production and purification of prodigiosin

The yield of crude prodigiosin (PG) produced by *S. marcescens* using 500 mL production medium was almost 1.0 g. This was obtained after liquid-liquid extraction of the pigment with petroleum ether and ethanol followed by drying at 45°C for 10 days (Figure 14 a and b).

Figure 14: (a) Production of prodigiosin by *S. marcescens*, (b) Extraction of crude prodigiosin by liquid-liquid extraction using petroleum ether and ethanol

The crude PG red pigment obtained (1.0 g) was purified by SPE (Figure 15). The yield of partially purified PG was 50 mg after drying at 45°C for 2 days in the oven for every batch of 500 mL peanut production medium.

Figure 15: Purified prodigiosin dissolved in methanol after solid phase extraction

6.2.2. Characterization of purified prodigiosin

6.2.2.1. Ultraviolet-visible (UV/VIS) spectrophotometry

The absorption spectrum of the red pigment PG in methanol showed a maximum absorbance peak at 538 nm (Figure 16).

Figure 16: Absorption spectrum of partially purified prodigiosin

6.2.2.2. Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) of partially purified prodigiosin

As shown in Figure 17, a characteristic band at 3393.1 cm^{-1} can be assigned to the amine group N-H. Moreover, the characteristics bands of methylene groups appeared at 2922.73 , 2853.48 , and 1446.3 cm^{-1} . The of C=O peak appeared 1742 cm^{-1} . The peak of O-H bending appeared at 1376.8 cm^{-1} . The finger-print region characterized by peaks at 1173.4 cm^{-1} and 722.3 cm^{-1} due to C-O group and C=C group, respectively were evidenced as shown in (Figure 17). The IR spectrum of the purified prodigiosin was almost quite similar to the reported IR spectrum of partially purified PG (Figure 18) ⁽²⁶⁰⁾.

Figure 17: FTIR spectrum of partially purified prodigiosin.

Figure 18: FTIR of purified prodigiosin from *S. marcescens* ⁽²⁶⁰⁾.

6.2.2.3. Liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS-MS)

The LC-MS-MS spectrum of the partially purified PG is depicted in (Figure 19). The m/z peak at 324 provided evidence for PG as reported previously⁽²⁶¹⁾.

Figure 19: LC- MS-MS spectrum of partially purified prodigiosin

6.3. Prodigiosin-lipopeptide biosurfactant (PG-LBS) nano-self-assemblies (nSAs)

6.3.1. Preparation of PG-LBS nSAs

Prodigiosin-lipopeptide biosurfactant nano-self-assemblies (PG-LBS-nSAs) were prepared by loading PG into LBS-nSAs by different procedures to increase the drug payload. Prior to the preparation of PG-LBS-nSAs, a solubility study was undertaken to determine the amount of PG that can be loaded at different LBS concentrations at room temperature (~25°C).

6.3.1.1. Solubility study

Similar to synthetic surfactants, biosurfactants are amphiphilic molecules that accumulate at interfaces, decreasing interfacial tensions and forming micelles as a result of molecular self-assembly⁽¹⁸³⁾. The critical micelle concentration (CMC) of crude lipopeptide biosurfactant produced by different bacillus strains was reported to range between 17.5 to 100 µg/mL⁽²⁶²⁻²⁶⁴⁾. In the present study, the ability of the partially purified lipopeptide biosurfactant (LBS) produced to increase the solubility of the poorly soluble PG, log $P_{\text{octanol-water}}$ 5.16⁽²¹⁹⁾ at ambient temperature (~25°C) was investigated. Based on literature data, LBS concentrations (100-800 µg/mL) were presumably higher than its predicted CMC. The concentration of PG solubilized was determined spectrophotometrically at λ_{max} 538 nm using a validated spectrophotometric assay. The calibration curve obtained indicated linearity over the PG concentration range 150-450 µg/ml (Figure 20). A coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.9987 was obtained from the linear regression analysis of the data (absorbance versus concentration).

Figure 20: Calibration graph for prodigiosin in methanol at λ_{\max} 538 nm.

PG assay was further validated for accuracy, inter-day precision and reproducibility. Accuracy is expressed by the % PG recovery while inter-day precision was presented by percent coefficient of variation (CV %). The % PG recovery of the test solutions of different concentrations varied from $83.89 \pm 1.2\%$ to $101.2 \pm 1.1\%$, indicating compliance with the requirements for drug analysis according to the ICH guidelines on validation of analytical procedures.⁽²⁶⁵⁾ Data of inter-day accuracy and precision are shown in Table 9. All CV % values were in the range of 0.67 to 2.9 %, pointing to precision of the method used for determining concentration.

Table 9: Inter-day precision and accuracy data for UV spectrophotometric assay of PG solutions in methanol at λ_{\max} 538 nm.

PG concentration, $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (Initial)	PG concentration, $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (recovered)	CV % (SD / Mean)	Mean PG recovery % Concentration recovered / Initial concentration
100	83.89 ± 1.2	1.40	83.89 ± 1.20
150	143.16 ± 4.7	3.20	95.40 ± 3.10
200	196.10 ± 5.7	2.90	98.00 ± 2.80
250	246.90 ± 1.8	0.72	98.76 ± 0.73
300	303.80 ± 3	0.98	101.20 ± 1.10
350	348.70 ± 5.7	1.60	99.62 ± 1.60
400	390.90 ± 2.6	0.67	97.70 ± 0.65
450	438.80 ± 3.2	0.72	97.50 ± 0.72

Table 10 illustrates the reproducibility of different calibration curves obtained on 3 different days, within one month. All CV % values ranged from 0.7 to 3.6 %, complying with the requirements for drug analysis. ⁽²⁶⁶⁾

Table 10: Reproducibility of various standard curves of PG in methanol at 538 nm performed on 3 different days.

PG concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance of PG			Mean PG absorbance value	CV %
	Run 1	Run 2	Run 3		
100	0.144	0.138	0.138	0.140 ± 0.002	1.4
150	0.284	0.261	0.284	0.276 ± 0.01	3.6
200	0.417	0.389	0.389	0.398 ± 0.01	2.5
250	0.521	0.512	0.512	0.515 ± 0.004	0.7
300	0.656	0.641	0.641	0.646 ± 0.007	1
350	0.768	0.74	0.74	0.749 ± 0.01	1.3
400	0.855	0.842	0.842	0.846 ± 0.006	0.7
450	0.967	0.951	0.951	0.956 ± 0.007	0.7

As indicated by the solubility data obtained using the assay method validated above, the concentration of PG dissolved in aqueous solutions of LBS increased as a function of the LBS concentration up to 500 µg/mL with leveling off of PG solubility at higher concentrations (Table 11). The maximum PG solubility attained in micellar LBS solution was 287.7 µg/mL under the study conditions.

Table 11: Effect of lipopeptide biosurfactant on the solubility of prodigiosin at ~25°C

Lipopeptide biosurfactant, µg/mL	Prodigiosin dissolved, µg/mL
100	171.0
300	260.9
500	287.7
600	287.7
800	287.7

The increase in the aqueous solubility of the water insoluble PG implied micellar solubilization of PG by BLS self-assemblies. The plateau observed in the solubilization of PG by LBS can be explained by a weaker interaction between the hydrophobic PG and LBS micelles compared with LBS-LBS interaction, probably destabilizing the formation of more micelles ⁽¹⁴⁾. In addition, the presence of hydrophobic molecules in the surfactant solution may alter the CMC and change the size and shape of the self-assembled structures in which they are solubilized ⁽²⁶⁷⁾.

The locus of solubilize within the surfactant micelles depends largely on the physicochemical properties of the surfactant, the molecular characteristics of the solubilize such as molecular size, hydrophobicity, and polarizability; the type of micelle formed as well as the properties of the solubilization medium, e.g. composition, ionic strength, pH, and temperature ^(268, 269). Because of the hydrophobic nature of PG, the drug molecules are most probably incorporated in the LBS micellar core ⁽²⁶⁹⁾. Incorporation of PG in the micellar core of various surfactants has been reported for different purposes. A main application involved the *in situ* recovery of PG from the interior of thalli (undifferentiated vegetative tissue) in culture media using micellar Tween 80 or Triton X-114 surfactant systems ^(270, 271). Solubilization of PG by LBS would also provide a bioinspired microbially derived system for pharmaceutical applications including drug delivery. A diagram for PG-LBS self-assemblies (PG-LBS nSAs) was hypothesized (Figure 21).

Figure 21: Proposed diagram of lipopeptide biosurfactant self-assembly incorporating prodigiosin

6.3.1.2. Preparation of prodigiosin-loaded lipopeptide biosurfactant nano-self-assemblies

In the present study, an attempt was made to prepare PG-loaded LBS self-assemblies as a potential drug delivery system. Micellar self-assemblies are known to exhibit an anisotropic water distribution resulting in water concentration decreasing from the surface towards the micelle core, conferring hydrophobicity to the core ⁽²⁶⁹⁾. Consequently, hydrophobic molecules such as PG will be entrapped within the core of micelles, improving their solubility and stability, two main requirements in drug delivery.

Preparation of PG-LBS-nSAs was undertaken using two methods for increasing the drug payload as much as possible. Method A, a two-step method, involved the preparation of LBS-nSAs followed by incorporation of PG in the preformed nanostructures using three different procedures while method B was based on simultaneous LBS-nSAs preparation and PG incorporation in one step. These preparation methods and procedures used are listed in (Table 4). The LBS concentration throughout the study (1mg/mL) was above the reported CMC values of lipopeptide biosurfactants ⁽²⁶²⁻²⁶⁴⁾ to ensure PG micellar entrapment. Whatman 0.2 μ filter paper was chosen as the filtering material to separate undissolved PG because PG was found to not to sorb to filter paper ⁽²⁷²⁾ and to sorb to membrane filters used.

6.3.2. Characterization of prodigiosin-biosurfactant nano-self-assemblies (PG-BS nSAs)

6.3.2.1. Drug content and entrapment efficiency (EE%)

The effectiveness of the entrapment methods and procedures utilized was judged by determining the EE%, LE% and stability of PG assessed as the time for appearance of signs of instability in terms of PG discoloration or precipitation from LBS-nSAs kept in the refrigerator (4°C). Results are shown in Table 12.

Table 12: Properties of PG-LBS-nSAs prepared by different methods and procedures

Formation of nano-self-assemblies in 1mg/mL LBS dispersion		PG loading method	EE%	LE%	Physical Stability at 4°C
Method A (Two step-method)					
Method A1	Vortex for 15 min	Sonication for 30 min at RT	< 1%	ND*	< 7 days
Method A2	Vortex for 5 min	Sonication for 30 min at 50°C	35.6 ± 9.7	50.88±6.94	14 days
Method A3	Sonication for 30 min at 50°C	Sonication for 30 min at 50°C	4.00 ±1.1	19.30±4.21	14 days
Method B (One step-method)					
Sonication of a mixture of BS (10 mg) and PG (30 mg) in 10 mL deionized water for 30 min at 50°C			13.85±1.65	29.25 ±2.45	2 days

*ND: Not determined

PG-LBS-nSAs prepared at room temperature (RT), ~ 25°C by method A1 involving vortexing of LBS solution for micelle formation, showed relatively low EE (0.15%) sign of instability at 4°C in 5 days. Using the same method by subjecting the LBS solution to sonication at higher temperature (50°C) (Method A2) resulted in enhanced PG solubility and PG-LBS-nSAs remained stable for 14 weeks. Temperature-enhanced micellar solubilization by many surfactants has been attributed to the increase in thermal agitation, resulting in an increase in the micellar space available for drug solubilization in addition to possible increase of drug solubility in water at higher temperatures⁽²⁷³⁾. Moreover, increased solubilization of hydrophobic molecules into the micelles tends to reduce the micropolarity of the micelle core, promoting further micellar entrapment⁽²⁷⁴⁾.

An attempt was made to further increase PG loading via ultrasound-assisted LBS micelle formation at 50°C for 30 min. This resulted in a drastic reduction in EE% and LE% (Table 12). PG loading achieved by simultaneous micelle formation and PG entrapment resulted in 13.85±2.45 EE% and 29.25±2.45 LE% but poorer micellar PG stability. Sound waves at the relatively high temperature appear to have affected the integrity of LBS micelles. It has been reported that the shear forces generated during sonication result in acoustic cavitation that affects the micelles' aggregation structures in an acoustic power-dependent manner ^(275, 276).

According to the results obtained, method A2 for PG loading provided a relatively high PG EE% and LE% in addition to relatively high stability compared to the other preparation methods. Thus, method A2 was selected for the preparation of PG-LBS nSAs for further experimentation. Furthermore, PG color stability in this formulation was assessed upon storage at 4°C in the refrigerator away from light for 14 days, and the residual color intensity was determined. PG in the methanolic solution exhibited a progressive reduction in absorbance at λ_{max} 538 nm that started at day 2 and attained 52.2% at day 14. On the other hand, entrapment of PG into LBS nSAs led to marked protection of the pigment. The pigment color was stable for at least 7 days and its reduction reached 15.5% only at day 14 (Figure 22). This provided further support to the selection of nSAs prepared by method A2. Enhanced stability of PG by LBS nSAs added to its enhanced solubility (Table 12) pointed to the potential of the nSAs of the prepared LBS as drug carrier.

Figure 22: Color stability of prodigiosin in LBS nSAs (navy blue column) in comparison with PG methanolic solution (blue column) over a 14-day study period at 4°C.

6.3.2.2. Morphology by transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

The ability of the LBS to form nSAs or nanomicelles was verified by TEM. Figure 23 shows TEM images of blank LBS nSAs (Figure 23a) and PG-LBS nSAs (Figure 23b) in distilled water.

Both nSAs were generally spherical in shape and not aggregated. The size and polydispersity of blank and PG-LBS nSAs (around 200 nm) confirming results found by dynamic light scattering ⁽²⁷⁷⁾.

Figure 23: TEM images of: (a) blank lipopeptide biosurfactant nano-self-assemblies (LBS nSAs) and (b) PG-LBS nSAs after 30-fold dilution. (X 50000 and 80Kv)

6.3.2.3. Colloidal properties

The ζ -potential and size distribution spectra of blank LBS nSAs and loaded PG-LBS nSAs, prepared by method A2 are shown in Figure 24 and Figure 25, respectively. The mean values for particle size, PDI and ζ -potential of the two test formulations are listed in Table 13. Data indicated good colloidal properties. The mean particle size was 231.9 ± 31.5 nm and 227.45 ± 18.95 nm for blank LBS nSAs and PG-LBS nSAs, respectively. PG loading generally had no effect on particle size. This was in agreement with data reported for many drugs and can be attributed to the presence of the drug in the core of the nano-self assemblies and not just attached to the surface ⁽²⁷⁸⁾.

Regarding size distribution, both LBS nSAs and PG-LBS nSAs formulations were generally moderately polydisperse as indicated by the PDI values (Table 13). The PDI is a measure of the heterogeneity of a nanomaterial sample based on size. Polydispersity can occur due to size distribution in a sample or aggregation of the sample. PDI values less than 0.05 indicate monodispersity, 0.05-0.7 mid-range polydispersity and > 0.7 high polydispersity ⁽²⁷⁹⁾. Polydispersity of the samples under study may be attributed to the partially purified nature of LBS. Furthermore, the use of sonication ⁽²⁸⁰⁾ or heat ⁽²⁸¹⁾ in preparation of nanomicelles was reported to generally produce nanomicelles with a relatively large size distribution.

Figure 24: (a) ζ -potential spectrum and (b) size distribution spectrum of blank LBS nSAs

Figure 25: (a) ζ -potential spectrum and (b) size distribution spectrum of PG-LBS nSAs

Table 13: Colloidal properties of blank lipopeptide biosurfactant nano-self-assemblies (LBS nSAs) and PG-LBS nSAs

Sample	Particle size (nm)	PDI	Zeta potential (mv)
LBS nSAs	231.9 ± 31.5	0.638 ± 0.2	-27.1 ± 0.9
PG-LBS nSAs	227.5 ± 18.9	0.562 ± 0.1	-29.5 ± 4.35

LBS nSAs showed a negative ζ -potential, -27.1 ± 0.9 mV and -29.45 ± 4.35 mV, for blank LBS nSAs and PG-LBS nSAs respectively (Table 13). This could be attributed to the anionic nature of LBS due to the presence of a small proportion of hydrolyzed biosurfactants, leading to a few negatively charged polar groups⁽²⁸²⁾. Many hydrogen bonds might be formed by the hydroxyl groups in the other corresponding groups. The produced hydrogen bonds might make the hydrogen atom of the hydroxyl groups prone to leave, inducing a negative zeta potential. It was also observed that, incorporation of PG into nSAs did not noticeably affect the surface as indicated by similar ζ -potential values. Again this observation confirmed that PG was uniformly distributed within the core of the nSAs and was not significantly adsorbed on the particle surface. Similar results were obtained by others⁽²⁸³⁾. Generally, ζ -potential indicates the degree of repulsion between close and similarly charged particles in the dispersion. A high ζ -potential indicates highly charged particles. This prevents aggregation of the particles due to electric repulsion and electrically stabilizes the nanoparticle dispersion. A ζ -potential value of 30 mV is enough for good stabilization of nanodispersions stabilized by electrostatic repulsion⁽²⁸⁴⁾. Colloidal properties data affirmed nano-size range of the LNS nSAs, moderate polydispersity and good stability.

6.3.2.4. Thermal analysis

Thermal stability of the PG-LBS nSAs is an important property for applications necessitating higher temperatures. Thermal analysis provides valuable information on the change in physical or chemical properties of materials as a function of temperature as well as potential interactions in a multicomponent system⁽²⁸⁵⁾. In the present study, PG, LBS and PG-LBS nSAs were subjected to a controlled temperature heating program at a rate of 10°C/min and the change in the sample mass and DTA were measured over the temperature range 40°C - 700°C. Results are shown in Figure 26.

Figure 26: TGA (red line) and DTA (blue line) curves of prodigiosin (PG), lipopeptide biosurfactant (LBS) and PG-LBS nano-self-assemblies (PG-LBS nSAs).

TGA of PG indicated gradual mass loss over the temperature range 100 to 700°C. About 4.8 % loss of PG weight over the temperature range 100°C to 160°C can be attributed mainly to elimination of moisture and partial decomposition of the ring structure. The weight loss (36.4%) observed between ~160°C to 500°C is probably due to further destabilization of PG rings⁽²⁸⁶⁾. Thermal decomposition of PG residues continued up to 700°C with ~ 35 % weight loss. The losses in PG mass were related to an exothermic peak at ~ 650°C as indicated by the DTA diagram.

TGA of LBS indicated high thermal stability up to 200°C. This was followed by a drastic decrease in mass (42.6%) over the temperature range 220°C to 430°C that can be related to an exothermic peak at 630°C as shown by DTA. Towards the end of the scan (700°C), the sample retained an almost fixed residual mass (51.3%), indicating thermal resistance of the LBS constituents. A nearly similar thermal degradation pattern has been reported for a lipopeptide biosurfactant produced by a marine *Nesterenkonia* sp,⁽²⁸⁷⁾.

Loading PG into LBS micelles resulted in nSAs with a different thermosensitivity pattern compared to the PG and LBS components. This can be described by increased sensitivity of the nSAs to the increase in temperature over the range 60°C to 150°C with a drastic loss in mass

(71.2%) and an exothermic peak at 100°C (DTA). Results of the thermal analysis are of importance regarding the storage and use of PG-LBS nSAs produced in the study.

6.3.3. Biological activity

The amphiphilic structure of biosurfactants including LBS endow these molecules with distinct physicochemical properties and biological activity driven mainly by their high surface activity and destabilization of biological membranes^(288, 289). The biological activity of LBS nanoformulations assessed in the thesis includes hemolytic activity of LBS nSAs in addition to the antibacterial and anticancer activities of PG-LBS nSAs.

6.3.3.1. Hemolytic activity

The hemolytic activity of lipopeptide biosurfactants has been the subject of extensive research⁽²⁹⁰⁻²⁹²⁾. Interestingly, the hemolytic activity of lipopeptide biosurfactants was utilized as the basis for quantifying their concentration in culture supernatants and to assess their toxicity^(293, 294). However, the hemolytic activity of biosurfactants is affected by variation in their chemical structure, concentration, and composition of the medium. In the present study, the hemolytic activity of blank LBS nSAs in the concentration range 100 to 700 µg/mL against human RBCs was assessed using PBS and 0.1% v/v Triton-X solution in deionized water as negative and positive controls, respectively. PG-loaded LBS nSAs could not be included in the study because of interference of the PG red color with hemoglobin absorbance.

Results shown in Figure 28 indicated that the calculated % hemolysis for the negative control and positive control were 0% and 100% respectively (Figure 27b). The LBS produced in the study did not induce measurable hemolysis of RBCs at all the test concentrations (Figure 27a), indicating negligible hemolytic activity. This may be attributed to the partially purified nature of the LBS produced by *B. lichiniiformis* or its inherent properties. As the properties of LBS produced by *B. lichiniiformis* have not been reported to date, the hemolytic activity of its purified form needs to be investigated. Nonetheless, negligible hemolysis of human RBCs by some biosurfactants has been reported and was considered a safety aspect of the biosurfactant⁽²⁹⁵⁾.

Figure 27: : Hemolytic activity of (a) the partially purified lipopeptide biosurfactant (LBS) compared to (b) negative control (PBS) and positive control (Triton-X 100).

6.3.3.2. Antibacterial activity

The antibacterial activity of PG-LBS nSAs in comparison with PG and LBS solutions was assessed using three MDR Gram-negative bacteria, *P. aeruginosa*, as well as *E. coli* ATCC 25922 and *E. coli* ATCC 35218 strains in addition to a standard *S. aureus* strain. Results are shown in Table 14. PG-LBS nSAs, PG and LBSnSAs showed no activity against *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa* (Figure 30,28). However, they were active against the MDR *E. coli* ATCC 25922 as indicated by the relatively low MIC values (Figure 30). It could also be observed that PG-LBS nSAs exerted an improved combinatorial effect against *E. coli* ATCC 25922 with a 0.6-fold reduction in MIC (Figure 29). Such enhancement by the PG LBS combination is in accordance with literature reports indicating marked enhancement of PG antibacterial activity against some microorganisms upon combination with biosurfactants^(233, 296). The other *E. coli* ATCC 35218 strain was more resistant to PG-LBS nSAs, LBS nSAs and PG with 11.3-fold increase in the MIC of PG relative to that for *E. coli* ATCC 25922.

Table 14: The antibacterial activity of prodigiosin (PG), partially purified lipopeptide biosurfactant (LBS) and PG-LBS nSAs

Bacterial strain	MIC (µg/mL)		
	PG	LBS nSAs	PG-LBS nSAs
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	-	-	-
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> ATCC 27853	-	-	-
<i>E. coli</i> ATCC 25922	12.7 ± 0.8	5.5±1.9	7.7± 1.9
<i>E. coli</i> ATCC 35218	143.5±10	-	-

N.B. Antibacterial activity values were expressed as the mean MIC values of two determinations ±SD

Although biosurfactants are known to exert bacteriostatic, bactericidal, and anti-biofilm activities by disrupting the microorganism cell membrane function and inhibiting the synthesis of cell membrane proteins, DNA, and RNA ^(159, 160), wide variability in microorganisms susceptible to biosurfactants has been reported. In fact, the antibacterial activity of biosurfactants depends on their interaction with the test microorganism which is largely affected by the type of biosurfactant, its microbial producer, effective concentration, purity, and mechanism of action in relation to the microorganism type, anatomical structure, and resistance. For instance, foodborne pathogenic and food spoilage microorganisms of both Gram-positive and Gram-negative types were found not susceptible to lipopeptide biosurfactants produced by *Bacillus sp.* ⁽²⁹⁷⁾. A lipopeptide biosurfactant produced by another *Bacillus sp.* (marine *Bacillus circulans*) showed similar results except for only one fraction of the crude biosurfactant eluted by HPLC which was found to possess high surface activity and a pronounced antimicrobial effect against a panel of Gram-negative and Gram-positive and pathogenic microorganisms including some MDR pathogenic clinical isolates ⁽²⁹⁸⁾. Heterogeneity of the results obtained in the present study could be attributed mainly to the partially purified nature of the LBS produced in the study and the antimicrobial resistance of three of the bacterial strains tested. However, an important conclusion to be drawn from these results is that the antibacterial activity of PG against a susceptible organism may be enhanced by nano-self-assemblies of an active biosurfactant, offering an advantage of the PG-LBS nSA system under study in antimicrobial drug delivery.

Figure 28 : Antimicrobial activity of self-assemblies using microdilution method and resazurin dye against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 27853

Figure 29: Antimicrobial activity of nano self-assemblies using microdilution method and resazurin dye against two bacterial strains : E. coli ATCC 25922 and E. coli ATCC 35218.

Staphylococcus aureus

Figure 30: Antimicrobial activity of self-assemblies using the microdilution method and resazurin dye against *Staphylococcus aureus*.

6.3.3.3. Anti-cancer activity

The anticancer activity of four test formulations, PG-LBS nSAs (3.12 - 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) in comparison with PG (3.12-100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), LBS (0.81-25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) and blank LBS nSAs (0.81-25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) was assessed using human breast adenocarcinoma MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 cell lines following 24 h and 48 h contact with the cancer cells at 37°C. MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 are commonly used cell lines for evaluating the *in vitro* activity of anticancer drugs. Both cell lines are invasive ductal/breast carcinoma cells, yet they have many phenotypic/genotypic differences: MCF7 are hormone-dependent (both estrogen and progesterone receptor positive), while MDA-MB-231 are triple negative⁽²⁹⁹⁾. MDA-MB-231 cells are generally used to model metastatic breast cancer⁽³⁰⁰⁾ and are known to be resistant to several anti-cancer agents⁽³⁰¹⁾. The anticancer activity of the test formulations in the current study was evaluated in duplicate using the MTT assay and DMSO 1% solution as control. The MTT (3-[4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl]-2,5 diphenyl tetrazolium bromide) assay depends on the conversion of MTT into formazan crystals by living cells, a property related to mitochondrial activity⁽³⁰²⁾. As the total mitochondrial activity in a cell population is related to the number of viable cells, the MTT assay is generally used to assess the *in vitro* cytotoxicity of drugs on cell lines.

Cell viability results obtained by the MTT assay indicated that all test samples reduced the viability of both cell lines in a time dependent manner (Figure 31). In other words, cytotoxicity was dependent on the contact time, higher activity being observed following 48 h- compare MCF-7 d with 24 h-contact with the cells.

Figure 31: Cell viability data for: (a) MCF-7 and (b) MDA-MB-231 cell lines. Results are the mean of two determinations.

Cell viability results were expressed as IC₅₀ values (concentration for 50% reduction in cell viability) which were determined using a polynomial regression equation. IC₅₀ data for MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 cell lines are listed in Table 15.

Table 15: IC₅₀ values for MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 cell lines following 24h and 48 h cell contact at 37°C.

Formulation	Concentration range, µg/mL	MCF-7 cell line		MDA-MB-231 cell line	
		IC ₅₀ , µg/mL ± SD		IC ₅₀ , µg/mL ± SD	
		24 h	48 h	24 h	48 h
PG solution	3.12 - 100	27.072±2.64	21.497±1.61	34.717±2.41	26.968±2.03
LBS solution	0.81 - 25	42.948±2.82	30.003±2.81	39.854±2.74	29.473±1.41
LBS nSAs	0.81 - 25	24.932±2.07	21.864±1.61	28.910±1.24	22.220±1.69
PG-LBS SAs	3.12 - 100	20.631±2.71	15.003±1.37	27.108±2.18	18.324±2.01

Plotting data in Table 15 resulted in the bar charts in Figure 32 a and b, for MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 cell lines, respectively.

Figure 32: IC₅₀ for (a) MCF-7 and (b) MDA-MB 231 cell lines following 24h and 48h exposure to the test formulations at 37°C. Error bars represent SD (n=2). In Figure 32, *denotes $p=0.0499$ and **denotes $p=0.00086$. In Figure 32B, ** denotes $p=0.0090$ and ns denotes statistical insignificance. Statistical analysis was carried out using one-way ANOVA by Graph pad prism 8.

According to the results obtained for the MCF-7 cell line following 24 h incubation: i) The cytotoxicity of PG was significantly ($p<0.0001$) greater than that of LBS (IC₅₀ 27.072 ± 2.64 vs 42.948 ± 2.82 µg/mL for PG and LBS respectively); ii) Self-assembly of LBS into nanomicelles significantly ($p<0.0001$) increased LBS cytotoxicity (IC₅₀ 42.948 ± 2.82 vs 24.932 ± 2.07 µg/mL for LBS and LBS nSAs, respectively) and iii) combining PG and LBS into nSAs increased the cytotoxicity of both PG and LBS (IC₅₀ 20.631 ± 2.71 µg/mL for PG-LBS nSAs vs 27.072 ± 2.64 µg/mL for PG and 42.948 ± 2.82 µg/mL for LBS).

Data obtained following 48 h-exposure indicated a further reduction in cell viability associated with lower IC₅₀ values for all test formulations. However, a trend of change in IC₅₀ values similar to that observed for the 24 h data was preserved. The IC₅₀ values were 21.497 ± 1.61 , 30.003 ± 2.81 , 21.864 ± 1.61 and 15.003 ± 1.37 µg/mL for PG, LBS, LBS nSAs and PG-LBS nSAs respectively.

A nearly similar trend of relative anti-cancer activity was observed for MDA-MB-231 (Table 15 and Figure 31b) in terms of both the ranking of activity of test formulations and the effect of contact time, though the cytotoxicity of all samples was lower compared with MCF-7 cell lines. Regarding the effect of LBS-nSAs on PG cytotoxicity, results indicated 23.8% and 30.2% increase in PG cytotoxicity against MCF-7 cells upon incorporation into LBS nSAs following 24 h and 48h contact, respectively.

For MDA-DB-231 cells, the cytotoxicity of PG-LBS nSAs was significantly ($p = 0.0059$) greater than that of PG after 24h exposure (IC₅₀ 27.108 ± 2.18 vs 34.717 ± 2.41 µg/mL for PG-LBS nSAs

and PG respectively). The increase in PG cytotoxicity as a result of its incorporation into LBS-nSAs, was 21.9 % and 32.1% for 24 h and 48 h exposure, respectively. Results pointed to the potential of LBS nSAs as bioactive drug carrier for drugs having anticancer activity.

The increased cytotoxic activity of the PG-LBS nSAs combination can be translated into a reduction in the dose of both PG and LBS nSAs as determined by the dose reduction index (DRI). This is a parameter indicating synergy of two bioactive agents and expresses the fold-decrease in the dose of either agent relative to their dose in the combination ⁽³⁰³⁾. Values for DRI obtained by analyzing the combined cytotoxic effect of PG-LBS nSAs and that of PG and LBS nSAs in both MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 cell lines at 50% cell death point are shown in Table 16. According to DRI data, the dose of PG and to a lesser extent that of LBS-nSAs can be reduced upon their combination into PG-LBS-nSAs as indicated by the fold increase in DRI. This ranged from 1.28 to 1.472 for PG and from 0.319 to 0.436 for LBS-nSAs. A larger dose reduction could be achieved at longer cell exposure time due to increased cytotoxicity. The fold-increase in DRI implies a similar fold-reduction in the PG dose in the PG-LBS-nSAs formulation, a finding of importance regarding safety.

Table 16: Dose Reduction Index (DRI) for PG and LBS-nSAs determined at 50% death point of MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 cell lines following 24 h and 48 h cell exposure at 37°C

Cell line/exposure time	Dose Reduction Index (DRI)	
	PG	LBS nSAs
MCF-7 24 h	1.312	0.361
MCF-7 48 h	1.433	0.436
MDA-MB-231 24 h	1.281	0.319
MDA-MB-231 48 h	1.472	0.363

Regarding cytotoxicity of the two components of the test formulations, PG and LBS, both agents are known to inhibit breast cancer cells. PG was reported to exert potent cytotoxic effects in both estrogen receptor positive (MCF-7) and estrogen receptor negative (MDA-MB-231) breast cancer cell lines via the mitochondrial pathway as indicated by cytochrome c release, activation of caspases-9, -8 and -7 and cleavage of poly (ADPribose) polymerase protein ⁽³⁰⁴⁾. Further studies indicated that the cytotoxic effect of PG on MCF-7 cells was achieved by inducing genomic damage via the formation of micronuclei in these cells ⁽³⁰⁵⁾, exerting proapoptotic effects by regulating apoptotic and antiapoptotic genes ⁽³⁰⁶⁾ and restoring the demethylation status and expression of miR-200c ⁽³⁰⁷⁾. Regarding inhibition of the more resistant MDB-MB-231 cells, PG was shown to induce mitochondrial-dependent apoptosis by downregulation of BCL2 and upregulation of BAX and caspase 9 mRNA transcription levels in these cells ⁽²³⁸⁾.

Lipopeptide biosurfactants were also reported to inhibit breast cancer cells, an effect initiated by a detergent-like effect that disrupts the cell plasma membrane, induction of apoptosis and capturing metastasis ^(308, 309). MCF-7 human breast-cancer cells were inhibited by the lipopeptide biosurfactant, surfactin and its isoforms produced by different Bacillus species in a dose- and time-

dependent manner ^(308, 310). More detailed analysis of surfactin-induced death of MCF-7 cells was related to the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and apoptosis via sustained activation of the phosphorylation of ERK1/2 and JNK signaling pathways ⁽³¹¹⁾. MDA-MB-231 triple negative breast cancer cells were also inhibited by surfactin by inducing cell cycle arrest at G1 phase ⁽³¹²⁾ and by suppressing metalloproteinase-9 (MMP-9) expression and TPA-induced phosphorylation of Akt and extracellular signal-regulated kinase (ERK) ⁽³¹³⁾.

Another important outcome of the cytotoxicity study is that the activity of the LBS nSAs against MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 cell lines surpassed that of free LBS solution. It is worth noting that comparison of the anticancer activity of biosurfactant solutions and their corresponding nanomicelles has not been documented to date. As the cell membrane disturbing effect of biosurfactants is involved in their anti-cancer activity, it can be assumed that the more pronounced LBS nSAs activity compared with free LBS can be attributed to enhanced nanomicelles-cell membrane interactions favoring internalization of LBS molecules.

The most important outcome of the cytotoxicity study is the potential of LBS nSAs as carrier system capable of enhancing the anticancer activity of PG, allowing for dose reduction as indicated by the DRI (Table 16). In fact, self-assembly nanostructures of lipopeptide biosurfactants were reported to modify the biological performance of entrapped therapeutic agents. For instance, micelle-like clusters of these biosurfactants were shown to ameliorate the internalization and antitumor activity of bleomycin ⁽¹¹⁾. Moreover, doxorubicin-loaded surfactin-based nanostructures allowed reversal of multidrug resistance in human breast cancer MCF-7/ADR cells ⁽¹⁰⁾ while its self-assembly with a gambogic acid-near-infrared dye conjugate into "mosaic-type" nanoparticles selectively targeted drug release into hypoxic cancer cells ⁽¹⁹⁴⁾. In addition, we demonstrated recently that incorporation of surfactin in lipid nanocapsules loaded with itraconazole, an antifungal drug having anticancer agent, significantly enhanced the treatment of intradermal tumor in mice with almost complete recovery of skin architecture ⁽²⁰³⁾.

Accordingly, cytotoxicity data obtained in the study do support literature data in underlining the potential of LBS nSAs produced in the thesis as drug carrier, particularly in anti-cancer therapy. However, further studies are needed to substantiate the results obtained.

7. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A biotechnological / pharmaceutical study was undertaken for the development of an entirely microbially-derived delivery system as a potential anticancer nanobiotherapeutic. This was based on a microbial lipopeptide biosurfactant (LBS) as carrier and a microbial secondary metabolite, prodigiosin (PG), as anticancer agent.

The carrier system consisted of the nano-self-assemblies (nSAs) of a partially purified biosurfactant produced for the first time by *B. licheniformis SHG10 DSMZ28096*. Physicochemical characterization using FTIR, gas chromatography and the emulsifying index provided evidence for the lipopeptidic nature of the biosurfactant and its surface active properties while hemolysis data indicated its hemocompatibility. Prodigiosin selected as a microbial anticancer agent was prepared and characterized in the study using UV/VIS spectrophotometry, FTIR and liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS-MS).

The preparation of PG-loaded LBS nSAs was based on a solubility study of PG in LBS solutions at 25°C. Blank LBS nSAs were generated by vortex mixing of a presumably post micellar LBS solution and PG loading was achieved subsequently by a sonication/heating method. The prepared PG-LBS nSAs were discrete spherical nanostructures with a mean diameter of 227.5 ± 18.9 nm, moderate polydispersity (PDI 0.562 ± 0.1) and a negatively charged surface (zeta potential -29.5 ± 4.35 mV). The PG entrapment efficiency and loading efficiency were 35.6 ± 9.7 % and 50.88 ± 6.94 %, respectively. Stability studies indicated physical stability of the prepared PG-LBS nSAs at 4°C for a 14 day-study period. Moreover, entrapment of PG in LBS nSAs enhanced its stability under the same conditions.

The anticancer activity of PG-LBS nSAs assessed in vitro using human breast adenocarcinoma MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 cell lines following 24 h and 48 h contact with the cancer cells at 37°C indicated a time-dependent anticancer activity that surpassed that PG and LBS. Such activity enhancement by LBS nSAs offers the advantage of PG dose reduction as indicated by the Dose Reduction Index (DRI). Furthermore, self-assembly of LBS into nanostructures significantly increased its cytotoxicity.

The thesis work provides a proof of concept for the suitability of the partially purified lipopeptide bisurfactant newly produced by *B. licheniformis SHG10 DSMZ28096* as a drug carrier in the form of nano-self-assemblies. By enhancing the solubility, stability and anticancer activity of PG as a microbial anticancer agent, the LBS nanostructures can be proposed as nanocarriers for drug delivery applications. However, further studies are needed to substantiate the results obtained using a purified form of the biosurfactant.

The present multidisciplinary thesis combining the efforts from the biotechnology, pharmaceutical and cancer disciplines add to the knowledge in the biomedical field regarding the use of the eco-friendly and sustainable biosurfactants in drug delivery applications. However, further studies are needed to substantiate the results obtained. In addition, more research efforts are required for improving the physicochemical properties and bioactivity of biosurfactants via chemical conjugation and incorporation in different nanostructures. Equally important, sufficient evidence has to be provided on the safety of biosurfactants as drug carriers or formulation components in various drug delivery systems. Finally, fundamental to the progression of biosurfactants in a wider range of biomedical applications, research efforts are needed to improve the efficiency of production technology and reduce the cost of production of biosurfactants.

8. SUMMARY

Biosurfactants are microbially derived surface active agents that are rapidly emerging as ecofriendly and effective substitutes to synthetic ones conventionally utilized in diverse industries. Biosurfactants offer great promise in the pharmaceutical field due to their high surface activity, bioactivity, low toxicity, biocompatibility, and biodegradability. Apart from their utilization as wetting, cleansing, solubilizing and emulsifying agents in pharmaceutical, personal care and detergent industries, biosurfactants possess drug-like actions, justifying their investigation as anti-microbial, anti-inflammatory, and anti-tumor agents. Moreover, biosurfactants may play multiple roles as formulation components in drug delivery systems with well-established advantages over conventional drug formulations.

The objective of the thesis was to provide data supporting the potential of biosurfactants in drug delivery applications. Developing a biosurfactant-based anticancer drug delivery system was the application selected. A lipopeptide biosurfactant (LBS) was targeted because of the surface activity and multiple biological functionalities of lipopeptide biosurfactants. Prodigiosin (PG), a secondary bacterial metabolite, was selected as the model drug because of its challenging lipophilicity and anticancer activity in addition to the lack of data on its delivery using biosurfactants. To the best of our knowledge, a combinatorial anticancer delivery system including nano-self-assemblies (nSAs) of a biosurfactant as a nanocarrier for PG has not been reported to date. This initiated the development of PG-loaded LBS nSAs as a bioinspired combinatorial delivery aiming at enhancing the solubility and anti-cancer activity of PG.

At the beginning, current literature information on biosurfactants was reviewed and presented as a brief introduction as well as a detailed knowledge background concerning biosurfactants, their chemical classification, producer microorganisms, main functional properties and biomedical applications. In the literature review, special emphasis was placed on biosurfactants in pharmaceutical drug delivery applications both as encapsulated bioactive agents or as drug delivery systems or formulation additives or emulsifiers.

In addition to the introduction and the literature review, the thesis comprises an experimental part designed to achieve the thesis objective. This part includes four sections: Preparation and characterization of a lipopeptide microbial biosurfactant; Preparation and characterization of prodigiosin as a microbial anticancer agent; Formulation of a biosurfactant-based prodigiosin delivery system and; Assessment of the anticancer activity of prodigiosin-loaded lipopeptide biosurfactant as a potential biotechnology-based biotherapeutic.

At first, a LBS was produced for the first time by *Bacillus licheniformis* SHG10 DSMZ28096 as a producer microorganism and partially purified via solid phase extraction and drying of the crude LBS resulted in a viscous honey-colored mass which was stored in the refrigerator (4°C) protected from light. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and gas chromatographic analysis indicated the lipopeptide nature of the isolated biosurfactant. The emulsifying efficiency of the LBS and its stability profile expressed as the emulsifying index at 24 h (E24) under different pH and temperature conditions provided evidence for the LBS emulsifying properties and its greater stability at neutral pH and 4°C. Moreover, a hemolysis study over the LBS concentration range 100 to 700 µg/mL using human RBCs indicated hemocompatibility of LBS.

Prodigiosin (PG), the highly lipophilic microbial red pigment used as model anticancer agent, was produced by *Serratia marcescens* and purified as reported. The purified PG was dried in the

oven at 37°C till almost complete solvent evaporation and kept at -20°C protected from light. Characterization methods including UV/VIS spectrophotometry, FTIR and liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry confirmed identity of the PG produced.

LBS and PG were then combined to generate a PG-LBS nanoformulation with potential anticancer activity based on LBS nano-self-assemblies (nSAs) as the carrier system. Prior to PG loading, a solubility study using a validated spectrophotometric assay indicated increased solubility of the sparingly soluble PG to 288 µg/mL by micellar solutions of LBS. The formation of LBS-nSAs and PG loading was achieved by different procedures. Judging by the PG entrapment efficiency (EE%) and loading efficiency (LE%) as well as physical stability over a period of 14 days at 4°C, a procedure involving the formation of LBS nSAs by vortex for 5 min followed by PG incorporation by sonication for 30 min at 50°C was selected. The generated PG-LBS nSAs showed EE% 35.6 ± 9.7 , LE% 50.88 ± 6.94 and physical stability for 14 days at 4°C. This formulation was further characterized for morphology by transmission electron microscopy (TEM), colloidal properties using Malvern ZetaSizer, FTIR and thermal analysis. Results indicated the formation of spherical nanostructures with a mean hydrodynamic radius of 227.5 ± 18.9 nm, moderate polydispersity (PDI 0.562 ± 0.1) and a negatively charged surface (ζ -potential -29.5 ± 4.35 mV). Moreover, entrapment of PG in LBS nSAs enhanced its stability at 4°C based on a change in PG absorbance at λ_{\max} 538 nm. FTIR analysis indicated preservation of the main spectral characteristics of PG and LBS in their physical mixture while thermal analysis denoted increased heat sensitivity of the PG-LBS nSAs relative to their components.

The last phase of the thesis work involved assessment of the biological performance of the in comparison with its components. As both LBS and PG are known to exert antimicrobial and anticancer activities, biological assessment involved these two activities. Values for the minimum inhibitory concentration, MIC in µg/mL of the test formulations determined using the standard broth microdilution against four microorganisms, standard *Staphylococcus aureus* and MDR *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 27853, *E. coli* ATCC 25922 and *E. coli* ATCC 35218 were heterogeneous. However, the antibacterial activity of PG against a susceptible microorganism (*E. coli* ATCC 25922) was enhanced by encapsulation in LBS nSAs.

More emphasis was placed on the anticancer activity of the developed PD-LBS nSAs, being the target application in the current thesis. The anticancer activity of PG-LBS nSAs assessed following 24 h and 48 h contact with human breast adenocarcinoma MCF-7 and the more resistant MDA-MB-231 cell lines using the MTT assay indicated time-dependent enhanced anticancer activity of PG-LBS nSAs that surpassed that PG and LBS. Such activity enhancement allows for potential PG dose reduction as indicated by the calculated Dose Reduction Index (DRI). Furthermore, self-assembly of LBS into nanostructures significantly increased its cytotoxicity.

In conclusion, the lipopeptide biosurfactant produced in the thesis using *Bacillus licheniformis* SHG10 DSMZ28096 as a new biosurfactant producer offers great promise in drug delivery applications owing to the ability of its nanostructures to incorporate the model drug PG with the formation of novel PG-loaded LBS nSAs that exhibit appropriate morphological and colloidal properties as well as enhanced anticancer activity, particularly against MCF-7 breast cancer cells.

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الملخص العربي

المواد المنشطة للسطح البيولوجية هي عوامل نشطة سطحياً مشتقة في أغلبها من الميكروبات باتت تكتسب أهمية متزايدة كبدائل فعالة وصديقة للبيئة للمنشطات السطحية الإصطناعية المستخدمة تقليدياً في العديد من الصناعات. فقد أصبح للمنشطات السطحية البيولوجية دوراً كبيراً في مجال المستحضرات الصيدلانية نظراً لنشاطها السطحي الملحوظ ونشاطها الحيوي وسميتها المنخفضة وتوافقها الحيوي وقابليتها للتحلل البيولوجي. فضلاً عن استخدام المنشطات السطحية البيولوجية كعوامل ترطيب وتطهير وإذابة وإستحلاب في الصناعات الدوائية ومستحضرات العناية الشخصية والمنظفات، فإن لها عدد من وظائف الأدوية مما يبرر إستعمالها كمادة مضادة للميكروبات والالتهابات والأورام. وعلاوة على ذلك، يمكن أن تلعب منشطات السطح البيولوجية أدواراً متعددة كحاملات دوائية ومكونات تدخل في صياغة أنظمة توصيل الدواء، مما يكسب هذه الصياغات مزايا كبيرة مقارنة بالتركيبات التقليدية.

تهدف هذه الرسالة إلى توفير النتائج التي تدعم إمكانية إستعمال منشطات السطح البيولوجية في تطبيقات توصيل الدواء. ولذلك تم تطوير نظام توصيل دوائي مضاد للسرطان يعتمد على منشط سطح بيولوجي كنظام حامل للدواء. وتم اختيار هذا المنشط من مجموعة الببتيدات الدهنية نظراً للنشاط السطحي والوظائف البيولوجية المتعددة لهذه المجموعة. كما تم اختيار مادة البروديغوسين وهو مستحلب بكتيري ثانوي، كدواء نموذجي وذلك بناء على نشاطه المضاد للسرطان بالإضافة إلى عدم تحميلة على نظام حامل من أصل ميكروبي من قبل. فعلى حد علمنا، لا توجد دراسات سابقة عن نظام توصيل مضاد للسرطان يعتمد على البروديغوسين كعامل دوائي وتجمعات نانومترية ذاتية لمنشط سطح بيولوجي كحامل نانومتري. فقد تم تحضير تجمعات نانومترية ذاتية لمنشط سطح بيولوجي من مجموعة الببتيدات الدهنية كنظام تحميل دوائي يساعد على ذوبان البروديغوسين وزيادة مفعوله المضاد للسرطان.

وقبل إجراء الدراسات العملية التي تحقق الهدف من الرسالة، تم الإطلاع على المعلومات المنشورة حول المنشطات السطحية البيولوجية وتقديمها على هيئة مقدمة موجزة وكذلك على هيئة خلفية معرفية مفصلة تناولت التصنيف الكيميائي لهذه المواد والميكروبات المنتجة لها وأهم خصائصها الوظيفية وتطبيقاتها الطبية الحيوية. بالإضافة إلى هذا، تشتمل الرسالة على جزء تجريبي تم تصميمه لتحقيق هدف الرسالة. يتضمن هذا الجزء أربعة أقسام: تحضير وتوصيف منشط سطح بيولوجي من النوع الببتيدي الدهني من مصدر ميكروبي، تحضير وتوصيف البروديغوسين كعامل ميكروبي مضاد للسرطان؛ صياغة نظام توصيل للبروديغوسين قائم على تجمعات نانومترية للمنشط السطحي البيولوجي الذي تم تحضيره وأخيراً تقييم نظام التوصيل الدوائي المكون من تجمعات المنشط السطحي والبروديغوسين كعلاج محتمل للسرطان قائم على التكنولوجيا الحيوية.

في البداية، تم تحضير المنشط السطحي البيولوجي لأول مرة بواسطة بكتيريا *Bacillus licheniformis* SHG10 DSMZ28096 باستخدام وسط زراعة متخصص. نتج عن التنقية الجزئية للمنشط السطحي الخام كتلة لزجة بلون عسلي تم تخزينها في الثلاجة عند درجة 4 مئوية بعيداً عن الضوء. بينت نتائج دراسات التوصيف الفيزيائي والكيميائي والتي شملت التحليل الطيفي للأشعة تحت الحمراء والتحليل الكروماتوغرافي للغاز إلى الطبيعة الببتيدية الدهنية للمنشط السطحي البيولوجي المحضر. كما دلت كفاءة الاستحلاب للمنشط السطحي على ثباتيته عند درجة الحموضة المحايدة و 4 درجات مئوية. علاوة على ذلك، أشارت دراسة انحلال كريات الدم الحمراء من أصل بشري إلى توافق المنشط السطحي المحضر مع الدم.

في الجزء الثاني من الدراسة، تم تحضير مادة البروديغوسين، الصباغ الأحمر الميكروبي شحيح الذوبان بواسطة بكتيريا *Serratia marcescens* للاستعمال كنموذج دوائي مضاد للسرطان. تم تحضير البروديغوسين وتنقيته وتجفيفه كما ورد في مراجع سابقة ثم حفظه عند 20- درجة مئوية بعيداً عن الضوء. أكدت طرق التوصيف، بما في ذلك القياس الطيفي للأشعة المرئية / فوق البنفسجية والتحليل بالأشعة تحت الحمراء والكروماتوغرافيا السائلة - قياس الطيف الكتلي الترادفي، التركيب الكيميائي للبروديغوسين المحضر.

تم في الجزء الثالث من الدراسة تحميل البروديغوسين على المنشط السطحي الببتيدي الدهني لتكوين صياغة نانومترية ذات مفعول محتمل مضاد للسرطان تقوم فيها تجمعات المنشط السطحي الذاتية النانومترية بدور نظام التوصيل. وقد تم إجراء دراسة لذوبان البروديغوسين في محاليل المنشط السطحي قبل تحميل البروديغوسين على تجمعاته الذاتية النانومترية وذلك باستخدام طريقة تحليل طيفية بعد التحقق من صحتها. أثبتت نتائج هذه الدراسة أن ذوبان البروديغوسين الشحيح في الماء قد زاد إلى 288 مجم/لتر عند درجة حرارة الغرفة. تم تحضير تجمعات المنشط السطحي الذاتية النانومترية وتحميلها بالبروديغوسين باستخدام عدة طرق اختبرت إحداها بناء على قيم كفاءة حوصلة البروديغوسين وكفاءة تحميلة وكذلك على الثبات الفيزيائي للنظام على مدى 14 يوماً عند درجة حرارة سالب 4 مئوية. وفقاً للطريقة المختارة، تم تحضير تجمعات المنشط السطحي الذاتية النانومترية

بتعريض محلول المنشط السطحي لحركة دوامية لمدة ٥ دقائق ثم تحميلها بالبروديجيوسين باستخدام الموجات فوق الصوتية لمدة ٣٠ دقيقة عند درجة حرارة ٥٠ مئوية. وبتوصيف تجمعات المنشط السطحي الذاتية النانومترية المحملة بالبروديجيوسين تبين أنها تتسم بكفاءة حوصلة 35.6 ± 9.7 في المائة وكفاءة تحميل 50.88 ± 6.94 في المائة وثبات فيزيائي لمدة ١٤ يوماً عند درجة حرارة سالب ٤ مئوية. أظهرت صور المجهر الإلكتروني النافذ أن تجمعات المنشط السطحي الذاتية اتخذت شكل كريات نانومترية كما أظهرت نتائج توصيف الخواص الغروانية لهذه الكريات أن متوسط قطرها الهيدروديناميكي يبلغ 227.5 ± 18.9 نانومتراً ومعامل تعدد تشتتها يبلغ 0.562 ± 0.1 وأن جهد زيتا لسطحها السالب الشحنة يبلغ -29.5 ± 4.35 mV. وقد أدى تحميل البروديجيوسين على تجمعات المنشط السطحي الذاتية النانومترية إلى زيادة ثابتية لونه الأحمر عند درجة سالب ٤ مئوية مقارنة بمحلول البروديجيوسين الحر في الميثانول وذلك بناء على قياسات التحليل الطيفي عند طول الموجة 538 nm. كما بينت نتائج تحليل الأشعة تحت الحمراء احتفاظ كل من البروديجيوسين ومنشط السطح الليبيدي الدهني في خليطهما بخصائصهما الطيفية الأساسية بينما أوضحت نتائج التحليل الحراري زيادة حساسية تجمعات المنشط السطحي الذاتية النانومترية المحملة بالبروديجيوسين للحرارة مقارنة بمكونيها.

في المرحلة الأخيرة من الدراسة، تم تقييم الأداء البيولوجي لتجمعات المنشط السطحي الذاتية النانومترية المحملة بالبروديجيوسين مقارنة بكل من مكونيها. وحيث أن لكل من المكونين مفعولاً مضاداً للبكتيريا ومضاداً للسرطان، فقد تم إدراج هذين المفعولين في التقييم. بينت نتائج الدراسة الميكروبيولوجية القائمة على تعيين التركيز المثبط الأدنى (MIC) باستخدام طريقة تخفيف المرق الميكروني القياسي تباين تأثير العينات موضوع الدراسة على أربعة أنواع من الجراثيم هي *Staphylococcus aureus* and *MDR Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 27853, *E. coli* ATCC 25922 and *E. coli* ATCC 35218. غير أن مفعول البروديجيوسين المضاد لأحدى السلالات الحساسة قد ازداد بتحميله على تجمعات المنشط السطحي الذاتية النانومترية.

وحيث أن التطبيق المستهدف في هذه الرسالة هو استخدام تجمعات المنشط السطحي الذاتية النانومترية المحملة بالبروديجيوسين كعلاج محتمل للسرطان، فقد تم التركيز على مفعول هذه التجمعات ضد نوعين من خلايا سرطان الثدي هما خلايا MCF-7 والخلايا الأكثر مقاومة للدواء MDA-MB-231. تم إجراء الدراسة على مدى ٢٤ و ٤٨ ساعة باستخدام طريقة MTT لتقييم حيوية الخلايا. بينت النتائج أن تجمعات المنشط السطحي الذاتية النانومترية تأثيراً مضاداً لسرطان الثدي يعتمد على تركيز التجمعات موضوع الدراسة وزمن تعرض الخلايا السرطانية لها. كما بينت النتائج أن تأثير التجمعات على هذه الخلايا يتجاوز تأثير كل من منشط السطح والبروديجيوسين. وقد أدت هذه الزيادة إلى إمكانية خفض جرعة البروديجيوسين وفقاً لحساب معامل خفض الجرعة. وإضافة إلى ذلك، أظهرت النتائج أن تجمع جزيئات منشط السطح الليبيدي الدهني ذاتياً على هيئة كريات نانومترية قد أدى إلى زيادة ملحوظة في مفعوله المضاد لخلايا السرطان.

وبذلك خلصت الرسالة إلى أن منشط السطح الليبيدي الدهني الذي تم تحضيره لأول مرة باستخدام *Bacillus licheniformis* SHG10 DSMZ28096 يتسم بتكوين تجمعات ذاتية نانومترية ذات خصائص فيزيوكيميائية وشكلية مناسبة لحمل البروديجيوسين كنموذج دوائي وتعزيز مفعوله المضاد لخلايا سرطان الثدي ولاسيما من نوع MCF-7 مما يعد تحقيقاً للهدف من الرسالة.